

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute

Volume 5: No. (2), June, 2022

President of the Journal : Prof. Dr. Ahmed Abd El Mageed

Editor –in-Chief : Prof. Dr. Shaaban Abd-Rabou

Secretary of the Journal

Prof. Dr. Shaaban Abd-Rabou

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Noha H. Ahmed

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Editorial Board Abroad

Dr. Alvin M. Simmons, FRES

Research Entomologist
USDA, ARS, U.S. Vegetable Laboratory
2700 Savannah Highway
Charleston, SC 29414
USA

Prof. Dr. Dong Chu

College of Plant Health and Medicine
Qingdao Agricultural University
No. 700, Changcheng Road
Chengyang, Qingdao, Shandong 266109
CHINA

Dr. Doo-Sang Park,

Korean Collection for Type Cultures (KCTC),
Microbiological Resource Center,
Korea Research Institute of Bioscience & Biotechnology (KRIBB), 125 Gwahangno,
Yuseong, Daejeon 305-806,
SOUTH KOREA

Dr. Gregory A. Evans

USDA/ APHIS/ PPQ c/o Systematic Entomology Laboratory
Bldg 005, Room 137,
BARC-WEST 10300 Baltimore Ave.
Beltsville, MD 20705
USA

Prof. Dr. Hassan Ghahari
Department of Entomology
Science & Research Campus
Islamic Azad University
Poonak – Hesarak
Tehran
IRAN

Dr. HDR. Hélène Delatte
UMR "Peuplements Végétaux et Bio-agresseurs en Milieu Tropical"
CIRAD-3P 7, Chemin de l'IRAT
Ligne Paradis
97410 Saint Pierre
La Réunion
FRANCE

Egyptian Editorial Board

Prof. Dr. Mohamed Ibrahim Abdel Mageed
University of Ain Shames
Faculty of Agriculture,
Cairo,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mohamed Gomaa Abbass
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Aly Soliman
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Aly H. El-Sherbiny
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Eman Radwan
Central Agricultural Pesticides Laboratory,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Magdy Welson
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mahmoud El-Naggar
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mohammad Hendi
Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute *is* an official journal of the Plant Protection Research Institute, *Agricultural* Research Center. It includes original research papers on basic and applied research in all aspects of plant protection. In additions to original research papers, also published reviews and scientific notes or short communications on critical issues relevant to plant protection. Subject areas include, but are not restricted to the following fields: Field pests, vegetable, aromatic, medicinal and ornamental plant pests, orchard pests, locust and grasshopper, beekeeping sericulture, spray technology, alternatives methods of control pests, survey and classification of agriculture pests and new biocontrol technology pests

Abbreviation of the Journal: Egypt. J. of Plant Prot. Res. Inst. `

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms (Lepidoptera) bibliography in Egypt

Abdallah, M. Al-Beltagy

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 4 / 4 /2022

Accepted: 15 / 6 /2022

Keywords

Bollworms,
bibliography, cotton
plant, control and
Egypt.

Abstract:

Bollworms (Lepidoptera) (Pink bollworm, spiny bollworm, and American bollworm) are a major serious cotton insect pest in Egypt, and it required a lot of control action using different Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and strategies, which requires a lot of research programs with so many research teams of works, which'll be noticed, recognized and seen here in this bibliography. Existing tactics for achieving a high degree of suppression of established bollworms populations are well advanced and feasible on a field-by-field basis. A combination of tactics may achieve even higher levels of pest suppression if implemented on an areawide basis. The longstanding nature of the pink bollworm problem in many areas of the world and the likely development of areawide management programs in the future prompted us to develop this bibliography as an information base to assist those in program planning, implementation, and evaluation. The bibliography should also be a useful aid to researchers, educators, extension personnel, agricultural producers, industry, and government administrators involved in managing this serious pest. This bibliography includes research papers about bollworms published in Egypt throughout along period from 1911 and up to. Almost these researches were carried out by Egyptian scientists from many different scientific research institutes, especially Plant Protection Research Institute (PPRI) and especially from Bollworms Research Department. Thanks to all those researchers who gave a hand in conducting and publishing these research papers included in this bibliography about pink bollworm *P. gossypiella*.

Acknowledgments

Sincere thanks to Prof. Dr. Shaaban Abd-Rabou and Reda A. Amer for scientific cooperation and for their insightful comments.

Bibliography of bollworms in Egypt (1911 – 2021)

Abbas, A.A.; Nada, M.A.; El-Sayed, A.A.; Abd-El-Hamid, N.A. and El-

Shenawy, R.M. (2017): Toxicity and latent effects of some control agents on pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 10(1): 25–34.

Abbas, M.S.T. (1982): Bracon brevicornis Wesm., a larval parasite of the pink bollworm. Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 58:233–238.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Abbas, M.S.T. and El-Deeb, Y.A.A. (1993):** On the natural enemies of the major pests infesting cotton in Egypt. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 71:131–138.
- Abbassy, M.A.; Ashry, M.; Adam, F.; Kahlil, F. and Abou-Shlou, M.A. (1984):** Toxicological and histopathological studies on the cotton bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent, 49:691–698.
- Abd El-Hafez, A.; Afifi, A.S.; Moustafa, A.A. and Ahmed, D.A. (2002):** Toxicological and biological studies on the effects of some biocides on pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). 2nd International Conference, Plant Protection Research Institute, Cairo, Egypt, 21-24 December.
- Abd El-Hafez, A.; Eissa, M.A.; Nada, M.A. and Girgis, M.F. (2004):** Effectiveness of *Trichogramma evanescens* (Westwood) on controlling pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* in cotton. Beltwide cotton conference, San Antonio, Cotton insect research and control conference, TX., 1463- 1469.
- Abd El-Hafez, A.; El-Lebody, k.A; Hassan, K.A. and Ahmed, D.A. (2009):** Histopathological effects of some biocides on the fourth abdomen segment of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 34(5): 5259-5268.
- Abd El-Hamid, N.A.; El-Sayed, A.A.; El-Sharkawy, A.Z. and El-Didamony, S.E. (2011):** Effect of emamectin benzoate on the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Egypt. J. of Appl. Sci., 26(10): 116-123.
- Abd El-Rahman, H.A. and El-Tahawe, H.S. (2020):** Effects of some pesticides, fungi and plant extracts against the two-spotted spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae*, predatory mite, *Amblyseius fallacies* and *Helicoverpa armigera* on cotton plant. Egy. J. Plant Prot. Res., 8(2): 653-674.
- Abd El-Rahman, Kh. A.; Ibrahim, M.M, and Ibrahim, S.M. (2003):** Effect of prevailing climatic conditions on the catch of male moths of *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.), *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera) by pheromone traps in El-Beheira Governorate. Egypt. J.Appl. Sci; 18(3): 350-365.
- Abd El-Zaher, T.R.; Kandil, M.A. and El-Sayed, A.A. (2012):** Evaluation of insecticidal activity and subsequent effects of thuja extract on *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). J. Egypt. Soc. Toxicol., 45:15-20.
- Abdallah, S.; Omar, A.; El-Tantawy, M.; Khidr, A.A. and El-Nabarawy, I. (1985):** The efficiency of certain insecticides against *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) and *Heliothis armigera* (Hübner). Alex. Sci. Exch., 6(2): 73-87.
- Abd-ElAzeem, E.M.; El-Sayed, A.A. and El-Gandy, R.M. (2020):** biological control of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) using spores and supernatants of some entomopathogenic fungi. Journal of Plant Protection and Pathology , Mansura Univ.,11(7):343-348.
- Abdel-Hafez, A. and Nada, M.A. (2000):** Augmentation of *Trichogrammatoidea bactrae* Nagaraja in the IPM program for control of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) in Egypt. Beltwide cotton conference, 1009-1013.
- Abdel-Rhman, Kh.A.; EL-Naggar, A.Z. and EL-Bassiouny, H.M. (2009):** Biological performance of certain green chemistry pesticides and mixtures against the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lepi.: Gelechiidae) (Saund) and spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Lepi.: Noctuidae) (Boisd.). 1st Nile Delta

- Conf. on Export Crops, Fac. of Agric., Minufiya Univ.: 335-345.
- Abdel-Salam, N.M.; Nada, M.A.; Hussein, A.M. and Rashad, A.M. (1994):** Abundance of spiny bollworm in relation to thermal heat units and host. *Al-Azhar J. Agric. Res.*, 19: 225-233.
- Abd-El-Samie, M. E.; Matar, A.M. and Megahed, F.M. (2004):** Effect of gamma irradiation on some biochemical aspects of the American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner). *National Center of Radiation Research and Technology Egyptian J. Appl. Sci.*, 19 (9A): 314-321.
- Abdo, M.Z.; Khidr, A.A.; Awad, H.A. and Mourad, A.K. (1991):** Population fluctuations of the cotton bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) and *Heliothis armigera* (Hübner). *Commun. Sci. and Dev. Res.*, 35: 125-131.
- Abou-Kahla, M.M.; El-Zanan, A.A.; El-Kady, M.B. and El-Deeb, A.S. (1990):** Evaluation of the toxic activity of four insecticidal groups upon *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.), *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) in relation to their side effects on fiber quality and some seed propereties. *J. Agric. Res., Tanta Univ.*, 16(1):121-132.
- Abou-Toor, H.B.; Abou-Kahla, M.M.; El-Zanan, A.A. and Helal, I.A. (1989):** The susceptibility of nine Egyptian cotton cultivars to infestation with cotton insect pests. *The 7th Arab Pesticide Conf., Tanta Univ., Sept.*, 11-12: 24-32.
- Affi, A.S.; Abd El-Hafez, A.; Moustafa, A.A. and Ahmed, D.A. (2007):** Insecticidal activity of some plant extracts against *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) in relation to their phenolic contents. *Egypt, J. Agric. Res.*, 85(1): 157-170.
- Ahmed, D.A. (2015):** Effect of vertimic, a microbial insecticide on the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gellichidae). A- toxicological and biochemical studies. *Minufiya J. of Agric. Res.*, 1(2): 169-178.
- Ahmed, D.A. (2015):** Effect of vertimic, a microbial insecticide on the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gellichidae). B- biological studies and life table parameters. *Minufiya J. of Agric. Res.* 40. 1(2): 179-186.
- Ahmed, D.A. (2019):** Fecundity, egg fertility and longevity of laboratory reared the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidea) under different adult diet regimes. *Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst.*, 2(1): 151-160.
- Ahmed, D.A. (2020):** Comparative studies under laboratory conditions of four selected insecticides on pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci. (F. Toxicology and Pest control)*, 12(2): 47- 61.
- Ahmed, D.A. (2020):** Free amino acids composition and its changes at developmental stages of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella*. *Egypt J. Agric. Res.*, 98(1): 1-10.
- Ahmed, D.A.; El-Sharkawy, M.A. and EL-Shennawy, R.M. (2019):** Role of amino acids in protecting *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) against strong protein-denaturing activity of phenolic compounds in cotton plants. *Egypt. J. Agric. Res.*, 97(2): 579-585.
- Ahmed, D.A.; El-Sharkawy, M.A.; Hassan, K.A. and Shairra, S.A. (2014):** Role of glycine in protecting *Pectinophora gossypiella* against strong protein-denaturing activity of phenolic compounds in cotton plants. *J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ*, 5(12): 1053-1063.
- Aioub, A.A.; Raslan, S.A.; Hassanein, S.S. and Hegab, M.E. (2003):** Effect of certain insecticides on the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Zagazig J. Agric. Res.*, 30(4):1711-1734.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Abdalla, E.F. (1991–1992):** Effect of sowing date and certain chemical control programs against the cotton bollworms *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* Boisd. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 19:157–165.
- Abdallah, M.D. and Zazou, H. (1971):** Evaluating cotton insecticides in UAR. World Crops, 23:68–71.
- Abdallah, S.A.; El-Sayed, E.I. and Nagy, M. (1980):** Timing of insecticidal applications for control of the pink bollworm. In Proceedings, 1st Conference Plant Protection Research Institute, Cairo, Egypt, December 13–15, pp. 47–56. Cairo: Plant Protection Research Institute.
- Abdel-Aal, Y.A.I.; El-Sebae, A.H.; Fahmy, M.F. and Ali, A.M. (1971):** Cholinesterase and anticholinesterase activity in cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.), and other lepidopterous larvae. Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 67:343–351.
- Abdel-Fatah, K.; El-Shaarawy, M.F.; Salem, Y.S. and El-Serwi, S.A. (1981):** The effects of larval food on the longevity, fecundity and rate of egg maturation of the pink bollworm moths *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 92:487–492.
- Abdel-Fattah, M.I.; Hosny, M.M. and El-Saadany, G. (1976a):** The rate and timing of nitrogenous fertilization to cotton plants as factors affecting populations of the bollworms, *Earias insulana* Boisd. and *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 60:75–83.
- Abdel-Fattah, M.I.; Hosny, M.M. and El-Saadany, G. (1976b):** The spacing and density of cotton plants as factors affecting populations of the bollworms, *Earias insulana* Boisd. and *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 60:85–94.
- Abdel-Fattah, M.M.; Algauhari, A.E.I. and Rostom, Z.M.F. (1972):** Some enzymes in the haemolymph of *Pectinophora gossypiella* during induction and termination of diapause. Journal of Comparative Physiology, 78:20–24.
- Abdel-Fattah, S.A.S.; Sharaf, I.M.F. and El-Sebae, A. (1983):** Performance of flucythrinate (Cybolt) against a wide spectrum of agricultural pests in Egypt [in Arabic; summary in English]. Arab Journal of Plant Protection, 1:74–78.
- Abdel-Galil, F.A.; Morsy, M.A.A. and Ali, A.M. (1982):** Effect of new insecticide on bollworms and associated biological control agents cotton fields. Assiut Journal of Agricultural Science, 13:219–227.
- Abdel-Hafez, A. (1995):** A comparison of thermal requirements and some biological aspects of *Trichogramma evanescens* Westwood and *Trichogrammatoidea bactrae* Nagaraja reared from eggs of the pink and spiny bollworms. Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo), 40:901–912.
- Abdel-Hafez, A. (2001):** A comparison of quality attributes and life table parameters of four trichogrammatids (Hymenoptera: Trichogrammatidae) reared from *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) eggs. Arab Universities Journal of Agricultural Sciences, 9:411–421.
- Abdel-Hafez, A. and Nada, M.A. (2000):** Augmentation of *Trichogrammatoidea bactrae* Nagaraja in the IPM programme for control of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) in Egypt. In Dugger, P. and Richter, D.A. eds., Proceedings, Beltwide Cotton Conferences, pp. 1009–1015. Memphis, Tennessee: National Cotton Council.
- Abdel-Hafez, A.; Abdel-Salam, K.A.; Taher, S.H. and Moawad, G.M.**

- (1995): Effect of some insecticides against *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) F1 larvae from gamma irradiated susceptible and cyanophos tolerant strains. *Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo)*, 40:417–424.
- Abdel-Hafez, A.; El-Banby, A.G.; Metwally, A.G. and Saleh, M.R.A. (1993):** Effect of exposure of pink bollworm during larval and pupal stages-or pupal stage only to high temperature. *Journal of Agricultural Research (Zagazig University)*, 20:369–378.
- Abdel-Hafez, A.; Moawad, G.M.; Abdel-Salam, K.A. and Taher, S.H. (1994):** Competitiveness of irradiated *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) moths, susceptible strain, to unirradiated moths of cyanophos tolerant strain. *Journal of Agricultural Research (Al-Azhar University)*, 19:213–223.
- Abdel-Hafez, A.; Taher, S.H.; Abdel-Salam, K.A. and Moawad, G.M. (1994):** Studies on the comparative radiosensitivity of susceptible and cyanox resistant strains of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Bollettino di Zoologia Agraria e di Bachicoltura*, 26:249–256.
- Abdel-Hafez, M.M.; Abdel-Sattar, M.M. and ElMalla, M.A. (1984–1985):** Changes in esterases, phosphatases and among amino-acid transferases of the pink bollworm moth during the course of insecticides poisoning. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*, 14:429–438.
- Abdel-Hamid, Z.H.; El-Fateh, R.S.M.; El-Saadany, G.B. and Romeilah, M.A. (1999):** Approximate number of annual field generations of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 77:575–589.
- Abdel-Megeed, M.; Naguib, M.I. and Hussein, N.M. (1986):** Pattern of vertical distribution of first instar larvae of pink bollworm in cyanophos treated and untreated cotton plants. *Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo)*, 31:787–798.
- Abdel-Megeed, M.I.; Watson, W.M.; Zidan, A.A.; Hegazy, G.M. and Hussein, N.M. (1987):** The ovicidal efficiencies of synthetic insecticides and insect growth regulators against the spiny and pink bollworm. *Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent*, 52(2b):495–499.
- Abdel-Raheem, A.A. and Alkaddoussi, A.R. (1991):** Mode of inheritance of resistance to cotton leafworm and bollworm in *Gossypium* sp. *Journal of Agricultural Research (Zagazig University)*, 18:475–486.
- Abdel-Rahim, W.A.; Metwally, S.M.I. and El-Dakroury, F. (1976):** Susceptibility of some Egyptian cotton varieties to the infestation by *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). *Journal of Agricultural Research (Tanta University)*, 2:332–338
- Abdel-Rahim, W.A.; Metwally, S.M.I. and El-Dakroury, F. (1980):** Effect of certain physical and chemical characteristics of cotton varieties on susceptibility to infestation by pink and spiny bollworms. *Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent*, 45:727–731.
- Abdel-Rahman, I.; El-Sufty, R. and Shenishen, L. (1983):** Ecological studies on *Ostrinia nubilalis* (Hbn.) and *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) during overwintering. *Journal of Agricultural Research (Tanta University)*, 9:1229–1237.
- Abdel-Rahman, S.I.; Naguib, S.M.; Ibrahim, A.A. and El-Enany, M.A.M. (1999):** Laboratory studies on the effect of the ectoparasitic mite *Pyemotes herfsi* (Oudemans) on the cotton bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). *Egyptian*

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Journal of Agricultural Research, 77:1217–1224.
- Abdel-Sattar, M.M. and El-Guindy, M.A. (1988a):** Effect of the juvenoid triprene on the biological activity of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 66:19–23.
- Abdel-Sattar, M.M. and El-Guindy, M.A. (1988b):** Joint action of insect growth-regulator pyrethroid mixtures on the biological activity of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 66:33–38.
- Abdel-Wahab, A.M. (1971):** Free amino acids in the haemolymph of six lepidopterous larvae species. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 54:81–85.
- Abdo, M.Z.; Awad, H.A.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Mourad, A.K. and Mesbah, H.A. (1991):** The efficiency of four new pheromone formulations in reducing the population density of the pink bollworm in El-Bohira Governorate. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 6 (12): 37-47.
- Abo-Elghar, M.R. and El-Rafie, M.S. (1968):** An evaluation of several insecticides on cotton pests. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 2:13–20.
- Abo-Elghar, M.R. and El-Rafie, M.S. (1969):** Effect of chemical treatments on cotton pests and cotton plants. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 3:55–74.
- Abo-Elghar, M.R., and Radwan, H.S.A. (1976–1977):** A laboratory method for evaluating granular pesticides against the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series 10:99–104.
- Abo-Elghar, M.R.; Radwan, H.S.A. and El-Keie, I.A. (1976–1977):** Effect of certain soil granular pesticides on two major cotton pests in Egypt. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 10:137–143.
- Abo-Sholoua, M.K.A.; Nassef, M.A. and Watson, W.M. (2000):** Changes in susceptibility of the larvae of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) to synthetic pyrethroids. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 78:665-673.
- Abou-Elhagag, G.H. (1998a):** Effect of spraying cotton plants during the early season against cotton aphid on cotton pests, natural enemies and some crop characters in Southern Egypt. Assiut Journal of Agricultural Science, 29:91–100.
- Abou-Elhagag, G.H. (1998b):** Seasonal abundance of certain cotton pest and their associated natural enemies in Southern Egypt. Assiut Journal of Agricultural Science, 29:253–267.
- Abou-Kahla, M.M.; El-Kady, M.B. and El-Sorady, A.E. (1993):** Efficiency of certain insecticides on bollworms infestation, fiber quality and seed properties of five cotton varieties. Journal of Agricultural Science (Mansoura University), 18:1825–1831.
- Abou-Kahla, M.M.; El-Sorady, A.E.M.; Salem, R.M. and Hussain, A.M. (1992):** Impact of several sequences of insecticides against certain cotton pests and the associated predator in cotton fields. Journal of Agricultural Research (Tanta University), 18:802–817.
- Aboul-Naga, A.M. and Ghanim, A.A. (1979):** Field sampling and estimation of loss caused by bollworms in Dakahlia Province. Journal of Agricultural Research (Alexandria), 27:647–653.
- Abul-Nasr, S.; Awadallah, K.T. and Omar, H.M. (1974a):** Oil and moisture contents of cotton bolls and seeds as factors inducing diapause in the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt 58:405–413.

- Abul-Nasr, S.; Awadallah, K.T. and Omar, H.M. (1974b):** Effect of aging of cotton bolls on diapause in the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 58:303–308.
- Abul-Nasr, S.E. (1980):** Virus and bacterial diseases affecting certain lepidopterous agricultural pests; *Spodoptera littoralis*, *Pectinophora gossypiella*, *Heliothis armigera*, *Ostrinia nubilalis* and *Pieris rapae*. In Report of PL-480 Project No. F4-ENT-13, pp. 1–26. Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt.
- Abul-Nasr, S.E.; Ammar, E.D. and Farrag, S.M. (1979):** Rates of infestation by *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) and *Earias insulana* Bois., on flowering sites of the cotton plant (Lepidoptera). Deutsche Entomologie Zeitschrift, 26:165–172.
- Abul-Nasr, S.E.; Ammar, E.D. and Merdan, A.I. (1978– 1979):** Field application of two strains of *Bacillus thuringiensis* for the control of the cotton bollworms *Pectinophora gossypiella* and *Earias insulana*. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 11:35–39.
- Abul-Nasr, S.E.; Ammar, E.D.; Merdan, A.I. and Farrag, S.M. (1979):** Infectivity tests on *Bacillus thuringiensis* and *Bacillus cereus* isolated from resting larvae of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lepidoptera, Gelechiidae). Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 88:60–69.
- Abul-Nasr, S.E.; Tawfik, M.F.S. and Hamburg, P.P. (1978):** Occurrence and causes of mortality among active and resting larvae of *Pectinophora gossypiella* [Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae] in Giza, Egypt. Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 86:403–414.
- Adair, E.M. (1911):** *Gelechia gossypiella* bred from *Thespesia populnea*. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 1:123.
- Adam, F.; Belal, A.H.; Ashry, M.A.; Abu-Shola, M.K. and Abbassy, M.A. (1984):** Effectiveness of some insecticides used to control the cotton pink bollworm in relation to their effects on fiber quality [Egypt]. Journal of Agricultural Research (Tanta University), 10:1415–1424.
- Afify, A.M.; Abdel-Samei, M.E.A. and Merdan, A.I. (1968):** Isolation and pathogenicity of three varieties of *Bacillus* associated with diseased cotton worms in Egypt. Proceedings of the Egyptian Academy of Science, 21:87–89.
- Ahmed, S.M.; Naguib, S.M.; Rashad, A.; Abdallah, M.Z. and El-Deeb, Y.A. (1993):** Comparison between somebody contents in different physiological cases of the 4th instar larvae of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.), Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae. Journal of Agricultural Research (Al-Azhar University), 17:249–258.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1990):** Integrated pest management against bollworms, as a means for insecticide rational and increase cotton production (in Arabic). Proc. of the Symposium of Integrated Pest Management, Pesticide Rational and Environmental Pollution, Nov. 7-8, Fac. of Agric., Alex. Univ., Alex., Egypt, Vol.1 (Moderation of Agric. Policy and Integrated Pest Management): 55-59.
- Abdo, M.Z.; Awad, H.A.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Mourad, A.K. and Mesbah, H.A. (1991a):** The efficiency of four new pheromone formulations in reducing the population density of the pink bollworm in El-Bohira Governorate. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 6 (12): 37-47.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shaker, N.; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991b):** The influence of pheromone traps on the infestation percentages and population density of bollworms in

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Alexandria and Al-Behera Governorates. Proc. of the 4th Arab Congress of Plant Prot., Cairo, 1-5 Dec., VII.111 (Pesticides and Toxicology): 477-487.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shaker, N.; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991c):** The efficiency of funnel and delta pheromone traps for bollworms. Proc. of the 4th Arab Congress of Plant Prot., Cairo, 1-5 Dec., 111 (Pesticides and Toxicology): 485-489.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shaker, N.; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991d):** Alternative methods for controlling bollworms. Alex. Sci. Exch., 12 (4): 775-794.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shaker, N.; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991e):** The influence of pheromone traps on the infestation percentages and population density of bollworms in Alexandria and Al-Behera Governorates. Abstract, Arab J. of Plant Prot., 10(1) : 93.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shaker, N.; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991f):** The efficiency of funnel and delta pheromone traps for bollworms. Abstract, Arab J. of Plant Prot., 10(1) : 94.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1991):** Cotton Insect – Complex interactions under pheromone and insecticide applications against pink bollworm. Ministry of Agric. and Land Reclam., Egypt., p.183 .
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1992):** A new tool in pink bollworm control " Combining gossyplore and insecticides ". Ministry of Agric. And Land Reclam., Egypt., p.129.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; S.S. El-Tabakh; M.A. Mourad; M.S. Shawir and G.M. Moawad (1993):** Effect of pheromone and conventional insecticides on cotton bollworms infestation, plant and yield properties. Egypt. J. Biol. Pest Control, 3 (1): 1-12.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shawir, M.S.; Mourad, M.A. and Moawad, G.M. (1993):** Preliminary evaluation of pheromone release in relation to pink bollworm infestation in cotton fields. Egypt. J. Biol. Pest Control, 3 (1): 13-19.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Salem, R.M.; El-Hamaky, M.A.; Abu-Aiana, R. and Omar, M.E. (1993):** Cotton aphid, Jassid and whitefly population dynamics under pheromone and insecticide applications against pink bollworm. J. Biol. Pest Control, 33 (1): 63-70.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; El-Mourshedy, M.M.; El-Deeb, A.S. and Mourad, A.K. (1993):** The role of light and sex-pheromone traps in monitoring the populations of certain lepidopterous cotton insects. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 8 (4): 287-302.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. and El-Adl, M.M. (1993):** Economics of cotton insect control under pheromone and insecticides. J. Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ., 18 (7): 1969-1993.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shawir, M.S.; Othman, E.A.; Abo-Elsaad, M.M. and Mourad, M.A. (1993):** Biochemical techniques for measuring susceptibility of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* to certain insecticides. Alex. J. Agric. Res., 38 (3): 393-411.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1993):** Pheromone application for pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders), control reduces number of insecticide applications. Abstract, Entomol. Soc. of Amer. (ESA), Annual Meeting, 12-16 Dec., Indianapolis, IN., USA.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1994):** Computer simulation models of cotton - insects under the Egyptian conditions. Ministry of Agric. And Land Reclam., Egypt., p. 130.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1994).** Population dynamics and density of some predators in cotton fields. Abstract, 5th International Symposium of

Neuropterology, 2-5 May, Cairo, Egypt.

- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; El-Mourshedy, M.M. and Mourad, A.K. (1994):** Pheromone traps for monitoring insecticide tolerance in three different lepidopterous insects, as an effective tool for insecticide resistance management. Abstract, Arab J. of Plant Prot., 12(1).
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1994):** Pheromone application for pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) control reduces the number of insecticide applications. Abstract, Proc. Crop Health Conf., 21-24 March, Fayoum, Egypt: 61.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1994):** Population dynamics and density of some common predators under alternative pink bollworm control programs. Abstract, Proc. Crop Health Conf., 21-24 March, Fayoum, Egypt: 119.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; El-Mourshedy, M.M. and Mourad, A.K. (1994):** Sticky traps for monitoring insecticide tolerance in three different lepidopterous insects, the effective tool for insecticide resistance management. Abstract, Proc. 5th Arab Congress of Plant Protection, 27 Nov. – 2 Dec., Fes, Morocco.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1995):** Computer simulation models of cotton _ insects under the Egyptian conditions, II. Triggering Bollworms Control Actions. Ministry of Agric. And Land Reclim., Egypt., p. 38.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. and Hamid, A.M. (1995):** Influence of sowing dates and wind direction on pink bollworm infestation in cotton fields treated with PB-Rope pheromone application. Proc. of 1st Int. Conf. of Pest Control, Mansoura, Egypt, 3-5 Sept.: 181-188.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Hamid, A.M. and Salem, A.A. (1995):** Efficacy of nine different control techniques (Pheromone and/or insecticides) on pink bollworm trap catches and boll infestation. Proc. of 1st Int. Conf. of Pest Control, Mansoura, Egypt, 3-5 Sept.: 197-204.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. and Hamid, A.M. (1995):** Cotton leafworm egg-mass collection and larval control under pheromone and insecticide applications against pink bollworm. Proc. of 1st Int. Conf. of Pest Control, Mansoura, Egypt, 3-5 Sept.: 469-476.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Hamid, A.M. and Moawad, G.M. (1995):** Different models of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) trap catches and boll infestation under different conditions. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 73 (4): 1019-1034.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; El-Mourshedy, M.M. and Mourad, A.K. (1996):** Pheromone traps for monitoring insecticide tolerance in three different lepidopterous insects, as an effective tool for insecticide resistance management. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 74 (1): 29-37.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Hamid, A.M. and Bartlett, A. (1996):** Susceptibility of pink bollworm three age classes of eggs and hatching larvae to five different insecticides. J. Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ., 21 (7): 2693-2701.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Hamid, A.M. and Naranjo, S. (1996):** Predaceous insects and sweet potato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* Genn. population dynamics in cotton fields in Arizona. J. Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ., 21 (9): 3309-3317.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. and Mohamed, I.G. (1996):** Pink bollworm different larval stages, spiny bollworm infestation and their trap catch relationships. J. Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ., 21 (9): 3319-3328.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Hamid, A.M. and Leggett, J. (1996):** Pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) pheromone trap position and boll infestation relationships in cotton fields

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- in Arizona. J. Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ., 21 (9): 3351-3359.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. and Haroun, N.S. (1996):** A new technique for pink bollworm suppression: "Sirene" attract and kill technique. Alex. Sci. Exch., 17 (4): 343-350.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; El-Deeb, A.S. and Barania, H.A. (1996):** Bollworm infestation indicator for comparing the efficiency of different control tactics. Alex. J. Agric. Res., 41 (3): 85-92.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2012b):** Semiochemicals : The Future of pest management . Proc. Of Minia Int. Conf. for Aric. And Irrig. In the Nile Basin Countries, 26th – 29th March 2012, El-Minia, Egypt : 257 – 270.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2012c):** Plant and insect semiochemical interactions in the cotton fields : Abstract Proc. of Alexandria International Cotton Conf., 17th – 18th April 2012, Alexandria, Egypt : p. 27.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2012d):** Pheromone Technology Applications In The cotton Fields In Egypt : Abstract Proc. Of Alexandria International Cotton Conf., 17th – 18th April 2012, Alexandria, Egypt : p. 28.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2012e):** Bt Transgenic Cotton : The world Future Of Cotton Production : Abstract Proc. Of Alexandria International Cotton Conf., 17th – 18 th April 2012, Alexandria, Egypt : p. 29.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shekeban, M.M.K.; Abo El-Amaym, M.M.; Kassem, S.M.I.; Mancee, A.H. and El-Arami, S.A. (2012a):** Assaying insecticidal efficacy of O.P.s against pink bollworm male moth field strains using the attracticide efficacy monitoring technique. Pest Management Newsletter , 21(2) : 7-13.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shekeban, M.M.K.; Abo El-Amaym, M.M.; Kassem, S.M.I.; Mancee, A.H. and El-Arami, S.A. (2012b):** Efficacy of pyrethroids against pink bollworm male moth field strains using the attracticide efficacy monitoring technique. Pest Management Newsletter, 21(2): 13-20.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2012f):** Semiochemicals: The Future of pest control. Lambert Academic Publishing GmbH & Co. KG and licensors, p. 79.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2012 g):** Insecticide resistance: The global problem of insect management. Abstract, ESA's Entomology Conference, November 11- 14, Knoxville, TN, USA.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2013a):** Pheromone technology applications in the cotton fields in Egypt . Proc. Of 2nd Alexandria International Cotton Conf., 10th – 11th April 2013, Alexandria, Egypt : 1-15.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2013b):** Bt. Transgenic cotton: The world future of cotton production. Proc. Of 2nd Alexandria International Cotton Conf., 10th – 11th April 2013, Alexandria, Egypt: 16 - 27.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2013c):** Transgenic Bt. Cotton applications in the developing countries. Proc. Of 2nd Alexandria International Cotton Conf., 10th – 11th April 2013, Alexandria, Egypt: 28 - 45.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2013d):** A new formula for estimating insecticide efficacy against bollworms under the Egyptian conditions. Abstracts – poster session, 2nd Alexandria International Cotton Conf., 10th – 11th April 2013, Alexandria, Egypt: 21.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2013e):** Cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) a main bollworm insect pest in Egypt . Abstracts – poster session, 2nd Alexandria International Cotton Conf., 10th – 11th April 2013, Alexandria, Egypt : 22.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2013f):** Bio – Technology and the Future of World Cotton Production. Lambert Academic Publishing GmbH & Co. KG and licensors, pp.143.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2013g) :** A new formula for estimating insecticide

Abdallah, M. Al-Beltagy

- efficacy against bollworms under the Egyptian conditions . Abstract, ESA's Entomology Conference, November 10- 13, Austin, TX, USA.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2013h):** A new formula for estimating insecticide efficacy against bollworms under the Egyptian conditions . Review of Literature, 1(5) : 1-5 .
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2013I):** Electrophoretical confirmation of insecticide resistance in bollworms field strains in Egypt. Pest Management Newsletter, 22(2) : 28-35 .
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2014a):** Insect pheromone technology: History, chemistry and applications. Pedia Press Publishing, Lightning Source UK Ltd, Milton Keynes UK. p. 118 .
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2015e): Pesticides :** Chemistry, toxicity and applications . Pedia Press Publishing, Lightning Source UK Ltd, Milton Keynes UK. p. 480.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2021a) :** A New formula for estimating insecticide efficacy against bollworms under the Egyptian conditions. 6th International Conference of PPRI, Future Prospects of Plant Protection, 10-12 October 2021, Cairo-Egypt, Abstract Book : p. 19.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2021b) :** Pheromone technology applications.in the cotton fields In Egypt. 6th International Conference of PPRI, Future Prospects of Plant Protection, 10-12 October 2021, Cairo-Egypt, Abstract Book: p. 20.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2021c):** Pheromone traps for the assessment of insecticides efficacy and monitoring insecticides resistance in insect field strains. 6th International Conference of PPRI, Future Prospects of Plant Protection, 10-12 October 2021, Cairo-Egypt, Abstract Book : p. 172.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2021d):** A New formula for estimating insecticide efficacy against bollworms under the Egyptian conditions, instead of the Henderson and Tilton (1955) formula . Egypt J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4(4) :499- 504.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2021e):** Pheromone traps for the assessment of insecticides efficacy and monitoring insecticides resistance in insect field strains. Egypt J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2021) 4(4) :585 – 599.
- Al-Beltagy, A.M. (2021f) :** Pheromone technology applications.in the cotton fields In Egypt with special references. Egypt J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst. (2021) 4(4) : 640-667.
- Alfieri, A. (1929):** The introduction of a parasite (*Microbracon kirkpatricki* Wilk) of the pink bollworm into Egypt. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 15:52– 56.
- Ali, M.A.; Hussien, A.E.; Raslan, S.A. and Hegab, M.A. (2007):** Evaluation of petroleum ether extract of Zanzalakht trees (Z-seed oil) on pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) [Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae]. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 85(4): 1205-1214.
- Al-shannaf, H.M. and Hegab, M.E. (2010):** Capture of pink and spiny bollworms male moths in relation to certain environmental factors and accumulate heat units. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 1(5): 251 – 263.
- Al-shannaf, H.M. and Hegab, M.E. (2010):** Effect of certain environmental factors on *Spodoptera littoralis* (boisd.) and *Helicoverpa armigera* (hüb.) capture male moths in relationship to accumulated heat units. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 88 (4):1153-1166.
- Amer, A.E. and El-Sayed, A.A. (2014):** Effect of different host plants and artificial diet on *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) development and growth index. Journal of Entomology, 11(5): 299-305.
- Amer, A.E. and EL-Sayed, A.A. (2015):** Larval food influence on number of spermatophores, fecundity and some biochemical parameters of the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). J.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 6(11):1527-1535.
- Amer, A.E. and El-Sayed, A.A. (2015):** Lower threshold temperature and thermal unit of American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner) reared on pea and lettuce and its rearing on new modified artificial diets. J. Product. & Dev., 20(3):273-284.
- Amer, A.E.; EL-Sayed, A.A. and Nada, M.A. (2009):** Development of *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in relation to heat unit requirement. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 87 (3):667-674.
- Amer, A.E.; El-Sayed, A.A. and Nada, M.A. (2009):** Development of American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in relation to heat unit requirement. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 87(3):667-674.
- Amer, A.E.; El-Sayed, A.A. and Raslan, S.A. (2010):** Improved techniques for laboratory rearing of the spiny bollworms *Earias insulana* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). J. Plant Protection and Pathology, Mansoura Univ., 1(5): 299-306.
- Amer, A.E.; Hashem, M.S. and El-Sayed, A.A. (2015):** Seasonal fluctuation of the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) on some host plants. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 6(10):1415-1425.
- Amer, R.A. and El-Nemaky, I.H. (2008):** Effect of some biocides on the biological and prediction parameters of the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund), (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control, 18(1): 65-74. Proceeding of 2nd Arab Conference of Applied Biological pest control, Cairo, Egypt, 7-10 April 2008.
- Amer, R.A. and El-Nemaky, I.H. (2012):** Effect of Two biocides on some biochemical determination in *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) and *Chrysoperia carnea* (Stephens). Egypt J. of Appl. Sci., 27(6):63-73.
- Amin, A.A.; Gergis, M.F. and Foda, M.E. (2001):** A simple empirical model for predicting the development and field generations of some cotton insect pests in Egypt. In Dugger, P. and Richter, D.A. eds., Proceedings Beltwide Cotton Conferences, pp. 1033–1041. National Cotton Council, Memphis, TN.
- Anan, R.A.; Hussein, N.M. and Ahmed, M. (1993):** Effect of pyriproxyfen on phosphatases and transaminases enzymes of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* Boisduval larvae. Journal of Agricultural Research (Al-Azhar University), 17:189–199.
- Anan, R.A.; Mohamed, M.I. and Hussein, N.M. (1993):** Biochemical effect of pyriproxyfen juvenoid on fat and haemolymph proteins of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo), 38:761–772.
- Andres, A. (1911):** Note sur un ravageur de la noix du cotonnier (*Gelechia gossypiella* (Saund.)) nouveau pour l’Egypte [Note on a pest of the cotton boll (*Gelechia gossypiella*) new for Egypt]. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 1:119–123.
- Andres, A.D. (1926):** Etwas über roten Kapselwurm. [Notes on the Pink Bollworm *Gelechia gossypiella* (Saund.) in Egypt]. Entomologie Zeitschrift, 40:49–52.
- Ashry, M.A., A.H. Hosny, and H. Ismail. 1978.** Field evaluation of some insecticides in combination on pink bollworm. Journal of Agricultural Research (Tanta University), 4:227–232.
- Awad, H A.; El-Naggar, A.Z.; EL-Bassiouny, H.M. and Tadros, H.M. (2014):** Evaluation of certain insect growth regulators and some insecticides against the cotton leaf worm and

- bollworms in field cotton and their effect on yield. *Alex. Sci. Ex. J.*, 35(2): 80 – 86.
- Awad, H.A. and Abdou, M.Z. (1988):** Sex pheromones as an aid in the pest management of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) and *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd) infesting cotton plants. *Journal of Agricultural Science (Mansoura University)*, 13:323–327.
- Awad, H.A.; El-Gogary, O.A. and Elewa, M.A. (1988):** Comparison on the relative efficiency of pheromones and insecticide treatments against the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Journal of Agricultural Science (Mansoura University)*, 13:311–316.
- Awad, H.A.; El-Naggar, A.Z.; EL-Bassiouny, H.M. and Tadros, H.M. (2014):** Efficiency of certain evaluated IGRs and conventional insecticides on the incidence of common lepidopterous insect-pests of cotton plant. *Alex. Sci. Ex. J.*, 35(2): 87–94.
- Awad, H.A.; El-Naggar, A.Z.; EL-Bassiouny, H.M. and Tadros, H.M. (2014):** Evaluation of certain insect growth regulators and some insecticides against the cotton leafworm and bollworms in field cotton and their effect on yield. *Alex. Sci. Ex. J.*, 35(2): 80-86.
- Awad, T.M. and Kandil, M.A. (1980):** Dosage-mortality studies of some recommended insecticides on the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). *Ain Shams University Research Bulletin*, 13:23.
- Awadalla, S.S.; El-Zanan, A.A. and Salem, R.M. (1991):** Studies on injurious insects infesting soybean plants and the efficiency of certain chemicals against these pests at Kafr El-Sheikh, Egypt. *J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ.*, 16(2):420-429.
- Ayad, F.A.; Ghoneim, Y.F.; Keddis, M.E.; Allam, A.M.; Mourad, E.I. and El-Guindy, M.A. (1993):** Toxicity indices of insecticides tested against field strains of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) during 1990 cotton season. *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 71:739–745.
- Azab, A.K.; Tawfik, M.F.S. and Nagui, A. (1968):** Studies on the biology of *Microbracon kirkpatricki* Wilk., in Egypt. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt*, 52:251– 271.
- Badawi, A. (1971a):** The effect of three insecticidal treatments on the infestation of cotton bollworms. *Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie*, 68:145–150
- Badawi, A. (1971b):** Studies on the cotton bollworms in the Sudan: Bionomics of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and the spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) infesting cotton. *Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie* 69:330–336.
- Badawi, A. (1974):** The susceptibility of certain American upland and sakel cotton varieties to bollworms infestation (Lepidoptera: Arctiidae and Gelechiidae). *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt*, 58:261–266.
- Badawi, A. and Mandil, F. (1972):** Studies on the cotton bollworms in the Sudan. II. The relative efficiency of an ultra-low volume formulation and certain other insecticides in the control of the two species of cotton bollworms. *Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie*, 70:62– 67.
- Badr, N.A.; Nada, M.A. and Mohamed, S.A. (1999):** Effect of Sex pheromone traps density on population of the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) in cotton fields. *Al-Azhar J. Agric. Res.*, 29: 211-222.
- Ballou, H.A. (1919):** Cotton and the pink bollworm in Egypt. *West Indian Bulletin (Barbados)*, 17:237–292.
- Ballou, H.A. (1920a):** The danger of invasion by pink bollworm. *Agricultural News (Barbados)*, 19:362.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Ballou, H.A. (1920b):** The pink bollworm (*Gelechia gossypiella* (Saunders) -In Egypt in 1916–1917. Cairo: Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Government Press.
- Ballou, H.A. (1918):** The pink bollworm (*Gelechia gossypiella*) in Egypt. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 11:236–245.
- Barania, H.A. and Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1996):** Regional and seasonal variations of pink bollworm trap catches and boll infestation relationships. *Alex. J. Agric. Res.*, 41 (3): 77-84.
- Barritt, N.W. (1929):** Experiments on the control of the Pink Bollworm in Egypt. *Bulletin of Entomological Research*, 20:41–43.
- Bishara, I. (1930):** Ratoon cotton in relation to insect pests. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin, 96.
- Bishara, I. (1936):** Some pink bollworm studies in Egypt. Ministry of Agricultural, Egypt, Bulletin ,163.
- Bishara, I. (1947):** Insect pests of cotton in Egypt. 2. The bollworm. *Egypt Cotton Gazette*, 2:71–80.
- Bishara, I. (1924):** Preliminary note on the estimation of loss by bollworm (*Pectinophora gossypiella*). Ministry of Agricultural, Egypt, Bulletin, 39.
- Bishara, I. (1928):** Preliminary experiments with dusting and spraying against insect pests of cotton. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin, 77.
- Bishara, I. (1954):** Some pink bollworm studies in Egypt. Part 2. The cotton sticks problem. Ministry of Agricultural, Egypt, Entomological Section, Technical Bulletin ,268.
- Bishara, I. (1954):** Some pink bollworm studies in Egypt. Part 3. Fighting the early bollworm moths. Ministry of Agricultural, Egypt, Entomological Section, Technical Bulletin, 269
- Bishara, I. (1954):** Some pink bollworm studies in Egypt. Part 4. Some small-scale experiments for pink bollworm control by means of insecticides. Ministry of Agricultural, Egypt, Entomological Section, Technical Bulletin, 270.
- Bishara, I. (1969):** Effect of agricultural factors on cotton yield and bollworm attack. UAR Ministry of Agriculture, Plant Protection Department, Technical Bulletin, 2.
- Bishara, I. (No date):** Bollworm effect on cottonseed and oil production. Cairo General Organization Government Print Office.
- Bishara, S.I.; El-Sawi, M.S. and El-Guindy, M.A. (1972):** Sensitivity to insecticides to full-grown larvae of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders), (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) during diapause. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*, 6:57– 66.
- Campion, D.G. and Honsy, M.M. (1987):** Biological, cultural and selective methods for control of cotton pests in Egypt. *Insect Science and Its Application*, 8:803–805.
- Campion, D.G. and Nesbitt, B.R. (1982):** Recent advances in the use of pheromones in developing countries with particular reference to mass-trapping for the control of the Egyptian cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* and mating disruption for the control of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella*. In *Les Mediateurs Chimiques Agissant sur le Comportement des Insectes*, Symposium International, November 16–20, 1981, Versailles, pp. 335–342. Paris: Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique.
- Cartwright, H.A. (1920):** Treatment of cotton in the field as a combative measure against *Gelechia* attacks. *Agricultural Journal of Egypt*, 9:126–128
- Critchley, B.R.; Campion, D.G.; McVeigh, L.J.; HunterJones, P.; Hall, D.R.; Cork, A. Nesbitt, B.F.; Marrs, G.J.; Justum, A.R.; Honsy,**

- M.M. and Nasr, E.A. (1983):** Control of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), in Egypt by mating disruption using an aerially applied microencapsulated pheromone formulation. Bulletin of Entomological Research, 73:289–299.
- Critchley, B.R.; Campion, D.G.; McVeigh, L.J.; McVeigh, E.M.; Cavannagh, G.G.; Hosny, M.M.; Nasr, E.S.; Khidr, A.A. and Naguib, M. (1985):** Control of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), in Egypt by mating disruption using hollow-fibre, laminate-flake and microencapsulated formulations of synthetic pheromone. Bulletin of Entomological Research, 75:329–345.
- Dewer, Y.; El-Bassoiny, H.M. and El-shahaat, M.S. (2016):** Improving the properties of emulsifiable formulation of pesticides in relation to efficacy against insect pests. iii. Adjuvants enhancing efficacy of cypermethrin and fenitrothion against the Egyptian cotton leaf worm, *Spodoptera littoralis*. Egyptian Scientific Journal of Pesticides, 3(3): 1-9.
- Dudgeon, G.C. (1913):** The pink bollworm. Agricultural Journal of Egypt, 2(2):1-5.
- Dudgeon, G.C. (1914):** The bollworm in Egypt. In Transactions, 3rd International Congress of Tropical Agriculture, London. London: J. Bale, Sons and Danielsson.
- Dudgeon, G.C. and Cartwright, W. (1917):** Treatment of cotton in the field as a combative measure against Gelechia attacks. Agricultural Journal of Egypt, 7:120–133.
- Dudgeon, G.C. and Gough, L.H. (1913):** Description of two braconids parasitic on *Earias*. Agricultural Journal of Egypt, 3:108–110
- Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture (1923):** Statistics of pink bollworm occurrence from 1916–1922. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin, Entomology Section, 27.
- Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture (1928):** Investigations of cotton pests. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Report of the Cotton Research Board, 7:45–48.
- Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture (1980):** Biological studies on *Parasierola* sp, a larval parasitoid of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 60:289–295.
- Eid, M.A.A. and Moursy, E.B. (1992):** Ascorbic acid analogue as a new type of male-sterilizing agent in moths of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Journal of Agricultural Science (Mansoura University), 17:911–918.
- EI-Naggar, A.Z and Tawfeek, M.E (2012):** Efficacy of some foliar fertilizers and alternative chemicals on the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) larvae (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) and their side effect on protease enzyme activity. J. Entomol., 9 (6): 375-381.
- EI-Naggar, A.Z; Ibrahim, G.M. and El-Agamy, E.I. (2008):** Toxicological and biochemical effects of some foliar nutrients and alternative compounds on the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), in relation to larval electrophoresis. J. Adv. Agric. Res., 13 (4): 607-627.
- Eiter, K., E. Truschiet, and M. Boness. 1967.** Neuere ergebnisse der chemie von Insektensexuallockstoffen synthesen von D, L-10 acetoxyhexadecen-(7-cis)-ol-(1), 12 acetoxyoctadecen-(9-cis)-ol-(1) (“Glyplure”) und l acetoxy-10-propyltri-decadien-(5-trans.9) [“Propylure”]. [New results of the chemistry of sex lure substances of insects. Synthesis of ...]. Justus Liebig’s Annals of Chemistry, 709:20–45.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- El Sayed, A. A.; Amer, A.E.; Zaki, A.A. and Hegab, M.E. (2017):** Effect of light and dark conditions on some biological and physiological aspects of *Helicoverpa Armigera* (Hübner). J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 8(10): 501–503.
- Ela, M.A.; Shafik, M.T.; Zaki, A.I. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1964):** The effect of toxaphene on cotton yield. Journal of Agricultural Research (Alexandria), 12:215–220.
- El-Abdallah, F.; Khalil, F.A. and Shoeib, A. (1984):** Influence of sowing date on rate of infestation by cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd), and pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund) and cotton yield. Journal of Agricultural Research (Tanta University), 10:1063–1071.
- El-Adl, M.A.; Honsy, M.M. and Champion, D.G. (1988):** Mating disruption for the control of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella*, in the delta cotton growing area of Egypt. Tropical Pest Management, 34:210–214.
- Elawad, S.A.; Gowen, S.R. and Hague, N.G.M. (2001):** Progeny production of *Steinernema abbasi* in lepidopterous larvae. International Journal of Pest Management, 47:17–21.
- El-Badry, E.; Rezk, G.N. and Hekal, A.M. (1975):** The external morphology of the adult *Parasierola* sp., a larval parasitoid of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Journal of Agricultural Research (Zagazig University), 2:309–322.
- El-Badry, E.; Rezk, G.N. and Hekal, A.M. (1980):** Biological studies on *Parasierola* sp, a larval parasitoid of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 60:289–295.
- El-Banby, M.A.; Salem, A.A.; Metwally, A.G. and Abdel-Hafez, A.M. (1989a):** Effect of gamma radiation on moths of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Journal of Agricultural Research (Minia University), 11:661–672.
- El-Banby, M.A.; Salem, A.A.; Metwally, A.G. and Abdel-Hafez, A.M. (1989b):** Influence of different constant temperatures on the biology of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Journal of Agricultural Research (Minia University), 11:691–708.
- El-Banby, M.A.; Salem, A.A.; Metwally, A.G. and Abdel-Hafez, A.M. (1989c):** Influence of high temperature during the larval and pupal stages on the emerging adult pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Journal of Agricultural Research (Minia University), 11:673–689.
- El-Banna, M.M.; Nasralla, A.K. and Omar, A.E. (1981):** Influence of synthetic pyrethroids and certain insecticide combinations on the fiber quality of Giza 70 in relation to their effect against *Pectinophora gossypiella*. Annals of Agricultural Science (Moshtohor), 16:291–304.
- El-Bassiouny, H.M.; Tadros, H.M. and El-Naggar, A.Z. (2015):** Cotton bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* control by biorational insecticides. Plant Prot. and path., Mansoura Univ., 6(12): 1703-1709.
- El-Bassiouny H.M.; Tadros, H.M. and Kordy, A.M. (2016):** Evaluation of consequent performed new insecticides regime for suppressing cotton bollworms and other non-target pests in cotton field. Egyptian Scientific Journal of Pesticides, 2(1): 86-90.
- El-Bassiouny, H.M. (2017):** An experimental study of certain neonicotinoid insecticides on the incidence of early infestation of the spiny and the american bollworms, growth and lint yield characteristics of cotton plants. J. plant prot. and path., Mansoura Univ., 8(10): 479–485.

- El-Bassouiny, H.M. (2021):** Environmental friendly technique to control cotton pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* in Egypt. International Journal of Tropical Insect Science, 41:1683-1687.
- El-Bassouiny, H.M.; Ahmed, A.F.; Madany, W.A. and Selim, S.H. (2022):** Impact of tetramic acid derivatives compounds against cotton lepidoptera pests' neonate larvae *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). International Journal of Entomology Research, 7(4): 170-176.
- El-Bassouiny, H.M.; Kandil, M.A. and Ahmed, A.F. (2021):** Comparative relationship between development time and fecundity as a fundamental tool in life tables parameters of prevailing strains of spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) in four governorates (Delta, Egypt). World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 10(8):111-124.
- El-Bassouiny, H.M.; Tadros, H.M. and El-Nagger, A.Z. (2015):** Cotton bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* control by biorational insecticides. Plant Prot. and path., Mansoura Univ., 6(12): 1703-1709.
- El-Deeb, A.L. and Zeid, M.I. (1961):** Histopathological studies of the effect of some insecticides on various tissues of the larvae of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) (Gelechiidae: Lepidoptera). Journal of Agricultural Research (Alexandria), 9:55-92.
- El-Deeb, M.A., M.M. El-Zohairy, K.A. Abdel-Salam, and A.H. El-Sherief. (1995):** Population dynamics and testis development of male pink bollworm moths captured in sex pheromone traps sited in cotton fields at Sharkia Governorate. Journal of Agricultural Research (Zagazig University), 22:533-544.
- El-Deeb, Y.A. (1998):** The efficiency of rectangle and funnel pheromone traps in suppressing the population of the cotton leafworm and bollworms. Alexandria Science Exchange, 19:465-479.
- El-Deeb, Y.A.; El-Hamaky, M.A. and Moawad, G.M. (1992):** The relative efficacy of capsulated sex pheromones in attracting male moths of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Journal of Agricultural Research (Al-Azhar University), 16:353-359.
- El-Deeb, Y.A.; El-Hamaky, M.A. and Moawad, G.M. (1993a):** Large scale use of pink bollworm (*Pectinophora gossypiella*) sex pheromone formulations integrated with conventional insecticides for the control of cotton pests in Egypt. Bulletin OILB/SROP, 16:213-219.
- El-Deeb, Y.A.; El-Hamaky, M.A. and Moawad, G.M. (1993b):** The relative efficacy of different capsules of sex-pheromones in attracting the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders), male moths in Egypt. Bulletin OILB/SROP, 16:220-223.
- El-Didamony, G.; El-Sayed, A.A. and Ali, A.A. (2016):** Toxic and biological effects of some endophytic bacteria on the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). The Eleventh Inter. Environmental Conf., Faculty of Science, Zagazig Univ., 407-421.
- Elewa, M.A. (1981):** Activity of synthetic pyrethroids on pink bollworms in relation to their effect on fiber quality of different gland and glandless cotton varieties. Annals of Agricultural Science (Moshtohor), 15:273-304.
- El-Fateh, S.M.; El-Hamaky, M.A.; Moawad, G.M. and Hussein, N.M. (1988-1989):** Large scale evaluation of pheromones in reducing the population density of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 17:19-28.
- El-Feel, E.A.; Khidr, A.A.; Abou-Kahla, M.M. and Abbas, M.G. (1991):** Effect of insecticidal sequence, time intervals between sprays, and early spray on the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders)

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- and cotton yield. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 69:73–81.
- El-Feel, E.A.; Khidr, A.A.; Abou-Kahla, M.M. and Abbas, M.G. (1991):** Effect of insecticidal sequence, time intervals between sprays, and early spray on the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) and cotton yield. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 69 (1): 73-81.
- El-Gammal, M.F. (1940):** Hot air treating machines used in the ginneries for the destruction of pink bollworm in the cotton seed. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin, 150.
- El-Garhy, M.S.; Shaaban, N.N.; Omar, B.A. and Morad, E.E. (1978–1979):** Effect of some granular soil insecticides on the control of certain cotton pests. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 11:219–227.
- El-Gayar, F. and Watson, W.M. (1981):** Effect of field application of dimilin on some cotton pests in Egypt. Journal of Agricultural Research (Alexandria), 29:271–275.
- Elghar, M.R.A.; Radwan, H.S.A. and El-Keie, I.A. (1975):** Effect of different spraying programs on the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* infestation and the yield of cotton (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 9:203–210.
- El-Gougary, A.O.; El-Deeb, A.S.; Hassan, N.A. and El-Sorady, A.E.M. (1993):** Effect of some pheromones on the population of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella*. Annals of Agricultural Science (Moshtohor), 31:1273–1283.
- El-Guindy, M.A. (1999):** Pesticide resistance management and optimization of integrated pest management programs in Egyptian cotton. Advances in Agricultural Research in Egypt (Special Issue), 2:1–52.
- El-Guindy, M.A.; Abdel-Sattar, M.M. and Keddis, M.E. (1983):** The effects of three synergists on the toxicities of certain insecticides to a tolerant field strain of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). International Pest Control, 25:150–152.
- El-Guindy, M.A.; Abdel-Sattar, M.M.; Dogheim, S.M.A.; Madi, S.M. and Issa, Y.H. (1982):** The joint action of certain insecticides on a field strain of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). International Pest Control, 24:154–155.
- El-Haidari, H.S.; Naoum, A.N. and Abid, M.K. (1969):** Pink bollworm on cotton. FAO Plant Protection Bulletin, 17:140.
- El-Hamaky, M.A.; El-Deeb, Y.A. and Watson, W.M. (1993):** Efficiency of different chitin synthesis inhibitors and conventional insecticides applied singly and in binary mixtures against bollworms infesting cotton. Journal of Agricultural Research (Tanta University), 19:708–717.
- El-Hamaky, M.A.; Moawad, G.M. and El-Fateh, S.M. (1987):** Effect of pheromones mixed with chelated foliar fertilizers on pink bollworm. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt 67:105–111.
- El-Hawary, I.S.; Shenishen, Z.; Tadros, M.S. and Ibrahim, M.M. (1995):** Effect of the foliar fertilizers, and the plant growth regulator on *Aphis gossypii* Glover., *Bemisia tabaci* Genn. and consequences on *Pectinophora gossypiella* infestation in cotton fields. Journal of Agricultural Research (Minufiya University), 20:1595–1603.
- El-Heneidy, A.H.; Abbas, M.S.T. and Khidr, A.A. (1987):** Comparative population densities of certain predators in cotton fields treated with sex pheromones and insecticides in Menofia Governorate, Egypt. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 16:181–190.

- El-Heneidy, A.H.; Khidr, A.A.; Matar, A.; Abdel-Halim, A. and Hegab, M.E. (2004):** Proper timing and number of releases of the egg parasitoid, *Trichogramma evanescens*, West for controlling the cotton bollworms in Egyptian cotton fields. Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control, 14(1):15-19.
- El-Keie, I.A.; Abo-Elhgar, M.R. and Radwan, H.S.A. (1976):** Field trials for screening of certain soil pesticides for the control of cotton pests in Egypt. Annals of Agricultural Science (Moshtohor), 5:113–118.
- El-Khawalka, M.H.; Omar, M.E. and Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1996):** Effect of pheromone and insecticide applications on the population densities of the red spider mite *Tetranychus cucurbitacerum* and its predator *Orius* spp. in the cotton field. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 74 (1) :39 - 51.
- El-Kifl, A.H.; Wahab, A.T. and Kahlf-Allah, A.M. (1969):** The use of gamma radiation for control or eradication of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 52:273– 276.
- El-Kordy, M.W.; El-Saedy, A.; Khidr, A.A. and Abdel-Aal, A.A. (1990):** Effects of some insect growth inhibitors on the biological activity of American bollworm, *Heliothis zea*. Al-Azhar J. Agric. Res., 12: 217-226.
- El-Lebody, K.A. and Ragab, M.G. (2007):** Influence of weather temperature and R.H. on bollworms population in pheromone treated cotton fields. Bull. Ent Soc. Egypt, 84: 13-2.
- El-Lebody, K.A.; Ahmed, D.A. and Mustafa, H.Z. (2013):** Some pathological features naturally infected field larvae of *Pectinophora gossypiella* in Upper Egypt. Bull. ent. Soc. Egypt, Econ. Ser., 90: 89-119.
- El-Lebody, K.A.; Halawa, S.M. and Ahmed, D.A. (2014):** Laboratory and field evaluations of two biocides and an insecticide against *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) and *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Research Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences, 10(1): 37-46.
- Elliger, C.A.; Chan, B.G. and Waiss, Jr. A.C. (1978):** Relative toxicity of minor cotton terpenoids compared to gossypol. Journal of Economic Entomology, 71:161–164.
- Elliger, C.A.; Zinkel, D.F.; Chan, B.G. and Waiss, Jr. A.C. (1976):** Diterpene acids as larval growth inhibitors. Experientia, 32:1364–1366.
- Ellington, J.J.; Norris, J.F. and Durkin. J. (1968):** A simplified field cage for trapping Pink Bollworm adults. Journal of Economic Entomology, 61:1468–1469.
- El-Lissy, O.; Al-Beltagy, A.; Antilla, L. and Leggett, J.E. (1994a):** Influence of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders), female age on oviposition capacity and egg hatchability. In Cotton Report, pp. 278–281. Arizona Agricultural Experiment Station Series P–96, Tucson.
- El-Lissy, O.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Antilla, L. and Leggett, J. (1994b):** Influence of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) female age on oviposition capacity and egg hatchability. Cotton, a College of Agric. Rep. Series P-96, Univ. of Arizona, USA: 278-281.
- El-Lissy, O.; Staten, R.T. and Antilla, L. (1993):** Control of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in Parker Valley, Arizona by mating disruption using commercial formulations of gossypure. In Proceedings of the International Cotton Pest Work Committee, pp. 114–117. Sacramento: California Department of Food and Agriculture.
- El-Minshawy, A.M.; El-Sherif, H.K.; Barrania, H. and Abdel-Hamid, M.M. (1991):** Monitoring of flight

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- catches of the 45 pink bollworm moths by sex attractant pheromone traps. *Journal of Agricultural Science (Mansoura University)*, 16:904–910.
- El-Naggar, A.Z. (2009):** Efficacy of some foliar fertilizers and alternative chemicals on the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) larvae (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). *Alex. J. Agric. Res.*, 54(1): 139 – 146.
- El-Naggar, A.Z. (1998):** Evaluation of certain foliar and micro-elements in an integrated pest management (IPM) program to control cotton bollworms. M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agric., (Saba-Bacha), Alex. Univ. Egypt pp. 176.
- El-Naggar, A.Z. (2003):** Evaluation of certain new approaches of control measures in an integrated pest management program of cotton bollworms. Ph.D. Thesis, Fac. Agric., (Saba-Bacha), Alex. Univ. Egypt pp. 232.
- El-Naggar, A.Z. (2013):** Impact of certain pesticides on urease and dehydrogenase enzymes in soil during the cotton bollworms control. *Alex. Sci. Ex. J.*, 34(1): 102–105.
- El-Naggar, A.Z.; Shekeban, M.M.; Ibrahim, M.M. and Metayi, M.H. (2012):** Evaluation of certain pesticides on cotton bollworms and cotton leafworm and their side effect on some prevalent sucking pests. *J. Adv. Agric. Res. (Fac. Agric. Saba Basha)*, 17(1): 1-20.
- El-Namaky, I.H.; Shalaby, M.A.M. and Amer, R.A. (2005):** Comparative studies between organophosphorus and pyrethroids insecticides on susceptibility and activities of acetylcholinesterase enzyme against the pink and spiny bollworm in Egypt. *Egyptian J. of Appli. Sci.*, 20(7): 277-287.
- El-Nawawy, A.S. and Lamie, O. (1978):** Control of spiny and pink (boll) worms in Egypt (during the cotton season). *Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent*, 43:667–676.
- El-Nawawy, A.S.; Ashry, M.A.; Lamie, O.; Abbassy, M.; Zein, A.; Massoud, A.H. and Abdel-Hafez, A.G. (1982):** Joint action of foliar fertilizers-insecticide mixtures on cotton leaf worm, boll worms and yield of cotton plants. *Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent*, 47:617–626.
- El-Nawawy, A.S.; Ashry, M.A.; Zein, A.A.; Masoud, A.H.; Abdel-Hafez, A.G. and El-Safty, R. (1983):** Foliar fertilizers, insecticides and their mixtures as protectants of cotton bolls against pink bollworm. *Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent*, 48:349–357.
- El-Nawawy, A.S.; Lamie, O.; Ashry, M.A.; Abdel-Rahim, W.; Matwally, S. and Hosny, A. (1976):** Evaluation of the activity of insecticides against spiny and pink bollworms. *Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent*, 41:1317–1321.
- El-Nawawy, A.S.; Lamie, O.; Hosny, A.H.; Abbassy, M.; Ashry, M.A. and Abdel-Rahim, W. (1977):** The sequences of different insecticides in one programme and its relation to control of different pests in A. R. Egypt. *Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent*, 42:943–947.
- El-Nawawy, A.S.; Lamie, O.; Salama, M.A.; Ashry, M.A.; Kadous, E.A.; Darrag, M. ; Toulan, M.; Hosny, A.A. and Abbassy, M. (1979):** Effect of several pesticides on the infestation with spider mites, white fly, jassids, aphids and boll worms in cotton fields in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate A. R. Egypt 1978. *Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent*, 44:205–222.
- El-Nemaky, I. H. I. (2005):** Efficiency of the parasitoid *Trichogramma*

- evanescens*, West. and the insecticidal applications as well as the predators against the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) in Egyptian cotton fields. Egypt J. of appl. Sci., 20 (6A): 282-292.
- El-Nemaky, I.H.I. and Azab, A.M.H. (2004):** Effectiveness of some benzoylphenylureas on the larvae of the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd). Egypt J. Agric. Res., 82(2):573-582.
- El-Nemaky, I.H.I.; Shalaby, M.A.M. and Amer, R.A. (2005):** Comparative Studies, between oranophosphorous and pyrethroids insecticides on susceptibility and activities of acetylcholine esterase enzyme against the pink and spiny bollworms in Egypt. Egypt J. of Appl. Sci., 20 (7): 277-287.
- El-Rafie, M.S., and Abo-Elghar, M.R. (1968):** Effect of chemical control on cotton pests. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 2:61-70.
- El-Refaei, S.A. and Emam, A.K. (1994):** Some factors affecting cotton aphids, whitefly, boll worms infestations and cotton yield. Annals of Agricultural Science Cairo, 39:431-439.
- El-Saadany, G. (1974):** A new light trap for controlling lepidopterous insect pests in Egypt. Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 77:136-141.
- El-Saadany, G., and Abdel-Fattah, M.I. (1975):** Contributions to the ecological studies on the cotton pests in Egypt. III. The effect of lunar phases on the nocturnal activity of certain Lepidoptera. Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 79:17-20.
- El-Saadany, G., and Abdel-Fattah, M.I. (1975):** On the nocturnal flight activity of some species of Lepidoptera injurious to cotton in Egypt [in German, summary in English]. Anzeiger Fur Schadlingskunde, Pflanzenschutz, Umweltschutz, 48:109-110.
- El-Saadany, G., and Abdel-Fattah, M.I. (1976):** Contributions to the ecology of cotton pests in Egypt. II. Plant factors influencing the distribution of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund). Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 80:35-40.
- El-Saadany, G.; El-Shaarawy, M.F. and El-Refaei, S.A. (1975):** Determination of the loss in cotton yield as being affected by the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and the spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 79:357-360.
- El-Saadany, G.B.; Hossain, A.M.; El-Fateh, R.S.M. and Romeilah, M.A. (1999):** The simultaneous effect of physical environmental factors governing the population activity of cotton bollworm moths. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 77:591-609.
- El-Salam, N.M.A.; Rashad, A.M.; Moawad, G.M. and El-Hamaky, M.A. (1992):** Initiation and evaluation of cotton bollworms control parameter on basis of counts of young larvae in the infested bolls. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 19:33-39.
- El-Sawaf, B.M.; Kaschef, A.H. and Soliman, A.A. (1968):** Development and histology of the scent gland of the cotton leafworm, *Prodenia litura* F., and the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (S.) (Lepidoptera). Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 61:229-239.
- El-Sayed A.A.; Amer, A.E. and Ragab, M.G. (2008):** Pink bollworm moths in relation to diapause, heat units and host plant. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, 85 :109-119.
- El-Sayed A.A.; Amer, A.E. and Ragab, M.G. (2008):** Pink bollworm moths in relation to diapause, heat units and host plant. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, 85 (4):909-921.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- El-Sayed, A.A. (2014):** Thermal units for the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in Sharkia and Kafr El-sheikh Governorates. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 92 (1): 81-90.
- El-Sayed, A.A. (2016):** Effect of sublethal dose of hexaflumuron on the ovary and egg maturation of spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). J. of Entomology, 13(1-2):26-32.
- El-Sayed, A.A.; Amer, A.E. and Abd-ElAzeem, E.M. (2020):** Effect of some Insecticides on Pink Bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), Associated Predators in Cotton Field and some of their Biochemical Effects. J. of Plant Protection and Pathology, Mansoura Univ., 11(2):147–151.
- El-Sayed, A.A.; Amer, A.E. and Zaki, A.A. (2013):** Effect of some different compounds on American bollworm *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) in cotton fields. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 4(2): 207-201.
- El-Sayed, A.A.; Amer, A.E.; Zaki, A.A. and Nada, M.A. (2013):** Relationship between developmental stages of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) in four governorates of delta Egypt and required thermal units. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 91(1):11-25.
- El-Sayed, A.A.; Kandil, M.A. and Amer, A.E. (2009):** Seasonal fluctuation of *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) on cotton and okra and heat units related. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 87 (4):909-921.
- El-Sayed, E.I.; Abdallah, S.A. and Nagy, M. (1980):** Ovicidal action of some insecticides on pink bollworm eggs of different ages. In Proceedings, 1st Conference of Plant Protection Research Institute, Cairo, December 13– 15, pp. 33–38. Cairo: EDICA.
- El-Sayed, E.M.; El-Sayed, A.A. and Amer, A.E. (2017):** Toxicity and biological effects of some bacterial isolates on American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) and Spiny Bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 8(8): 379 –383.
- El-Sayed, M.T. and Abdel-Rahman, H.A. (1960):** On the biology and life history of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 44:71–90.
- El-Sayed, M.T. and Rostom, Z.M.F. (1960a):** Factors affecting initiation of the resting stage of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 44:253–264.
- El-Sayed, M.T. and Rostom, Z.M.F. (1960b):** Factors affecting termination of the resting stage of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 44:265–282.
- El-Sayed, M.T.; Soliman, A.A. and Rostom, Z.M.F. (1963):** A study of the fumigant toxic action of some volatile chemicals on the resting stage of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 46:473–477.
- El-Sebae, A.H. and Ahmed, Y.M. (1973):** Factors affecting efficiency of some organotin compounds against cotton leaf and boll worms. Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 72:367–376.
- El-Sebae, A.H.; Zeid, M.A. and Saleh, M.A. (1993):** Status and environmental impact of toxaphene in the third world— a case study of African agriculture. Chemosphere, 27:2063–2072.
- El-Shaarawy, M.F.; El-Saadany, G. and El-Refaei, S.A. (1975):** The economic threshold of infestation for the cotton bollworms on yield in Egypt. Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 79:276–281.

- El-Shaarawy, M.F.; Khalifa, A.; Metwally, A.G. and Abdel-Hafez, A. (1980):** Rearing pink bollworm on cottonseed meal diet. In Proceedings, 1st Conference of Plant Protection Research Institute, Cairo, December 13–15, pp. 33–38. Cairo: EDICA.
- EL-Shahaat, M.S.; EL-Naggar, A.Z. and Eshra, E.H. (2010):** Improving the properties of emulsifiable formulation of pesticides in relation to efficacy against pests. From Academic to Pesticide Industry Conf., 24 – 25 March 2010, Dep. of Pesticide Chemistry and Technology, Fac. of Agric. Alex. Univ. Egypt.
- El-Sharaby, A.M.; Salama, H.S. and Aziz, R. (1980):** Gustation and olfaction in Lepidopterous insects. *Annals of Agricultural Science (Moshtohor)*, 13:177–187.
- El-Sharkawy, M.A.; EL-Shennawy, R.M. and Ahmed, D.A. (2020):** Free amino acids composition and morphological ultrastructure of *Pectinophora gossypiella* and *Sitotroga cerealella* eggs used as alternative hosts for rearing the egg parasitoid *Trichogramma*. *Egypt J. Plant Pro. Res.*, 8(1): 34 – 51.
- El-Sheakh, A.A.; Salem, I.B.; Khidr, A.A.; Desuky, W.M. and Raslan, S.A. (1995):** Biochemical parameter in the pink bollworm under sequential use of insecticides in field application. *Egypt. J. of Appl. Sci.*, 10 (3): 313-321.
- El-Sheikh, F. M.; Abo-Seda, S.A.B. and Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1993):** Laboratory and field studies on the effect of certain insecticides, IGR, insecticide mixtures, IGR's and oils on *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saun.) (Lep., Gelechiidae). *Egypt. J. Appl. Sci.*, 9 (2): 513-524.
- El-Shennawy, R.M.; Ahmed, D.A. and El-Sharkawy, M.A. (2019):** Comparative studies on the free amino acid composition in the total body homogenate of some Lepidopterous and Neuropterous insects. *J. Plant Prot. and Path.*, Mansoura Univ., 10(8): 391 – 395.
- El-Sherbeni, A.E.; Mesbah, I.I.; Khidr, A.A.; Kishk, S.A. and Seleman, L.E. (2010a):** Relationship between different control methods and biochemical aspects in bollworms. *Egypt. J. of Appl. Sci.*, 25 (2B): 42-60.
- El-Sherbeni, A.E.; Mesbah, I.I.; Khidr, A.A.; Kishk, S.A. and Seleman, L.E. (2010b):** Role of some integrated pest management elements in controlling bollworms in cotton fields. *Egypt. J. of Appl. Sci.*, 25 (2B): 61-76.
- El-Sherbeni, A.E.; Mesbah, I.I.; Khidr, A.A.; Kishk, S.A. and Seleman, L.E. (2010c):** Comparative studies of the efficacy of different control methods integrated with mass-trapping against bollworms, *Egypt. J. of Appl. Sci.*, 25 (2B): 28-41.
- El-Sherif, H.K.; El-Minshawy, A.M.; Barrania, H. and Abdel-Hamid, M.M. (1991):** Susceptibility of cotton cultivars to infestation with the larvae of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). *Journal of Agricultural Science (Mansoura University)*, 16:893–897.
- El-Sherif, H.K.; El-Minshawy, A.M.; Abdel-Hamid, M.M. and Barrania, H. (1991):** Effects of semiartificial diets on some biological parameters of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). *Journal of Agricultural Science (Mansoura University)*, 16:918–923.
- El-Sorady, A.E.; El-Feel, E.A.; El-Shouny, K.Y. and El-Zanan, A.A. (1994):** Effect of different formulations of *Pectinophora gossypiella* pheromone and insecticides on moth populations, predaceous insects, flower and boll infestation and cotton yield. *Egypt. J. Appl. Sci.*, 9(11):191-201.
- El-Sorady, A.E.; El-Zanan, A.A.; Abo-Sholoo, M.K. and El-Dahan, A.A. (1998):** Influence of some insecticide sequences on natural and artificial infestation with pink bollworm,

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Egypt. J. App. Res., 76(2): 385-397.
- El-Sorady, A.E.M.; El-Zanan, A.A.S.; Abo-Shloa, M.K.A. and El-Dahan, A.A. (1998):** Influence of some insecticide sequences on natural and artificial infestation with pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 76:585–597.
- El-Tahawe, H.S. (2020):** Impact of chromones compounds on some biological aspects of the three cotton bollworm species under constant temperature. J. Plant Pro. Res. Inst., 3(2): 544-549.
- El-Tahawe, H.S.; Shahawy, W.A. and Hegab, M.E. (2018):** Toxicological and biological effects of some synthetic organic compounds on pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) laboratory strains. Egypt Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 10(2): 23-34.
- El-Tahawe, H.S.; Soliman, M.H.; Elnagar, H.M. and Soma, H.M. (2019):** Impact of adding chitosan on bio- efficacy to some insecticides against cotton spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) infesting cotton crop and yield measurable under field conditions. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 2(4):622-628.
- El-Tantawy, M.A. and Khidr, A.A. (1981):** Toxicities and morphogenetic action of some juvenoids against the American bollworm, *Heliothis zea* (Boddie.). Zagazig J. Agric. Res., 8:249-253.
- El-Tantawy, M.A.; Ashour, M.B. and Khidr, A.A. (1982):** Effect of enzymatic inhibitors on the toxicity of organophosphorus insecticides against the American bollworm, *Heliothis zea* (Boddie.). Proc. 2nd Egyptian-Hungarian Conf. of Plant Protection, Alex., 412-420.
- El-Tigani, M.E.A. and Khagali, M.A. (1978):** Pink bollworm in Barakat Block. In Annual Report of the Gezira Research Station 1970–1971, pp. 98–100. Agricultural Research Corporation, Sudan Ministry of Agriculture.
- El-Zanan, A. A. (1996):** Influence of sex ratio, moth age and intermingling period on some biological aspects of the bollworm. J. Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ., 21(12): 4491-4498.
- El-Zanan, A. A. (1998):** Bollworm's infestation and cotton yield as influenced by water regims. Egypt. J. App. Res., 76(2):607-614.
- El-Zanan, A. A. and Watson, W. M. (1998):** Effect of cotton planting dates and prevailing weather factors on pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) infestation. J. Agric Sci. Mansoura Univ., 23 (3): 1293-1301.
- El-Zanan, A.A.; Abo-Shloa, M.K.; Nassef, M.A. and Watson, W.M. (1998):** Seasonal abundance of certain cotton pests as affected by prevailing weather factors in Dakahlia governorate. J. Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ., 23(5): 2219-2239.
- El-Zanan, A.A.; Khlafalla, E.M. and Salem, R.M. (1994):** Effect of pheromone and recommended insecticides of pink bollworm against non-target insects and associated predators in cotton fields. J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 19(11):3947-3955.
- El-Zanan, A.A.S. (1998):** Bollworms infestation and cotton yield as influenced by water regime. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 76:607–614.
- El-Zanan, A.A.S. and El-Hawary, I.S. (1999):** Infestation with cotton leafworm and bollworms in relation to pheromone and light trap catches in cotton fields. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 77:647–661.
- El-Zik, K.M.; Grimes, D.W. and Thaxton, P.M. (1989):** Cultural management and pest suppression. In R.E. Frisbie, K.M. El-Zik, and L.T. Wilson, eds., Integrated Pest Management Systems and Cotton

- Production, pp. 11–36. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- El-Zohairy, M.M.; El-Deeb, M.A.; Abdel-Salam, K.A. and El-Sherief, A.H. (1995):** The damage assessment and estimation of the injury level caused by pink bollworm. *Journal of Agricultural Research (Zagazig University)*, 22:521–532.
- El-Zoheiry, M.S. (1950):** Ratoon cotton as a trap crop for the pink bollworm, *Platyedra gossypiella* (Saund.). In *Proceedings, 8th International Congress Entomology, Moscow, Russia*, pp. 737–738.
- Farghali, A.A.; Ragab, M.G. and El-Nenaey, H.M. (2002):** Laboratory and field evaluation of nuclear polyhedrosis virus as biological control agent of *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in cotton. 2nd International Conference, Plant Protection Research Institute, Cairo, Egypt, 21-24 Dec., 1: 339-342.
- Ferriere, C. (1929a):** The Asiatic and African species of the genus *Elasmus* Westw. (Hym.: Chalcid). *Bulletin of Entomological Research*, 20:411–423.
- Ferriere, C. (1929b):** On three new chalcidoid parasites of *Platyedra*. *Bulletin of Entomological Research*, 20:255–259.
- Ferriere, C. (1935):** Descriptions de deux importants Chalcidiens d’Egypte et du Soudan. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt*, 19:365–370.
- Feshawi, A.A.; Guirguis, M.W.; Watson, M.W. and Nassef, M.A. (1991):** Studies on the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) II. Chemical control programs for the cotton pink bollworm. *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 69:89–98.
- Feshawi, A.A.; Guirguis, M.W.; Watson, M.W. and Nassef, M.A. (1992):** Studies on the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). III. The possibility of using sex pheromone [Gossyplure] within a chemical control program to combat pink bollworm in cotton fields. *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 70:507–517.
- Fikry, R.M.; Ismael, N.A.; Raslan, S.A. and El-Tahawe, H.S. (2017):** Acute and biological effects of some synthetic organic compounds on spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). *J. Agric. Res. Cen.*, 95(2):599-611.
- Foda, M.E. (1998):** Spatial distribution patterns of two cotton bollworms *Pectinophora gossypiella* and *Earias insulana* in Qaulubia Governorate, Egypt. In P. Dugger and D.A. Richter, eds., *Proceedings, Beltwide Cotton Conferences*, pp. 1230–1232. Memphis, Tennessee: National Cotton Council.
- Gaaboub, I.A.; Kelada, N.L. and Abdel-Ghany, A.A. (1985):** Field evaluation of virelures 1 & 2, zealure and (Z)- 11-hexadecenal/(Z)-9-tetradecenal (29:1) as sex pheromones for moths of the African cotton bollworm *Heliothis armigera* (Hubner) and others under the Egyptian conditions. *Journal of Agricultural Research (Alexandria)*, 30:1049–1060.
- Gadallah, A.I.; Emara, S.A.; Hosein, N.M.; El-Kordy, M.W. and El-Fatma M. N. (1990):** Effect of gamma irradiation on the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo)* 35(Special issue):469–478.
- Gadallah, A.I.; Khidr, A.A.; Ali, M.A. and Moursi, M.A. (1990):** New approach for the control of the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *J. Pest Control & Environ. Sci.*, 2: 189-199.
- Gergis, M.F. and Younis, A.M. (1993):** Cotton bollworms: Male moth catches in pheromone traps and relationship to oviposition and boll infestation in cotton fields in Middle Egypt. In D.J. Herber and D.A. Richter, eds., *Proceedings, Beltwide Cotton Conferences*, pp. 1048–1051. Memphis, Tennessee: National Cotton Council.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Gergis, M.F.; El-Hamaky, M.A. and El-Duweini, F.K. (1993):** Spray as needed philosophy based on egg-sampling and larval age structure for improved management of pink bollworm. In D.J. Herber and D.A. Richter, eds., Proceedings, Beltwide Cotton Conferences, pp. 877–882. Memphis, Tennessee: National Cotton Council.
- Gergis, M.F.; Hamid, A.A.; Mostafa, S.A. and Foda, M.E. (2001):** Biologically-based new approaches for management of cotton key pests in middle Egypt. In P. Dugger and D.A. Richter, eds., Proceedings Beltwide Cotton Conferences, pp. 876-882. National Cotton Council, Memphis, TN.
- Gergis, M.F.; Moftah, E.A.; Soliman, M.A. and Khidr, A.A. (1990):** Temperature-dependent development and functional responses of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Assiut J. Agric. Sci., 21 (3): 119-128.
- Gergis, M.F.; Moftah, E.A.; Soliman, M.A. and Khidr, A.A. (1990):** Temperature-dependent development and functional responses of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella*. Assiut Journal of Agricultural Science, 21:119–128.
- Gomaa, E.A.; Moawad, G.M. and Khidr, A.A. (1982):** Phosphatases activity in different stages of the American bollworm, *Heliothis zea* (Boddie.). Proc.2nd Egyptian-Hungarian Conf. of Plant Protec.: 63-69.
- Gomaa, E.A.; Tantawy, M.A. and Khidr, A.A. (1982):** Esterases activity in different stages of the American bollworm, *Heliothis zea* (Boddie.). Proc.2nd Egyptian-Hungarian Conf. of Plant Protec.: 53-61.
- Gough, L.H. (1914a):** A parasite of the pink bollworm [*Pimpla roborator* Fabr.]. Agricultural Journal of Egypt, 3:103.
- Gough, L.H. (1914b):** Entomological notes. Agricultural Journal of Egypt 3:103–104.
- Gough, L.H. (1914c):** Problems relating to the new pest of Egyptian cotton, the pink bollworm, *Gelechia gossypiella* (Saunders) [in French]. Bulletin Union Agriculture, Egypt (Cairo), 12(107):196–197.
- Gough, L.H. (1916a):** Note on a machine to kill *Gelechia* larvae by hot air, and the effects of heat on *Gelechia* larvae and cotton seeds and on cotton seed. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin 6 (Entomology Section).
- Gough, L.H. (1916b):** Problems connected with the new Egyptian cotton pest, *Gelechia gossypiella* (Saund.), the pink bollworm. In Transactions, 3rd International Congress Tropical Agriculture, London, pp. 385–398. London: J. Bale, Sons & Danielsson.
- Gough, L.H. (1916c):** The life history of *Gelechia gossypiella* from the time of the cotton harvest to the time of cotton sowing. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Sciences Service Bulletin 4 (Entomology Section).
- Gough, L.H. (1916d):** The nature of the damage done by the pink bollworm, *Gelechia gossypiella* (Saund.). Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin 2.
- Gough, L.H. (1917a):** On the rate of increase of *Gelechia gossypiella* larvae in green bolls during 1916. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 4:113–115.
- Gough, L.H. (1917b):** Preliminary notes on the infestation of *Hibiscus esculentus* pods by the pink bollworm. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 4:79–82.
- Gough, L.H. (1917c):** The rate of increase of the pink bollworm in green bolls in period July to November 1916. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin 13.

- Gough, L.H. (1919):** On the effects produced by the attacks of the pink bollworm on the yield of cotton seed and lint in Egypt. *Bulletin of Entomological Research*, 9:279–324.
- Gough, L.H. (1920):** The pink bollworm in Egypt. In Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, *Bulletin*, 106: 472–532.
- Gough, L.H. (1922):** On the dispersion of the pink bollworm in Egypt. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, *Technical Science Service Bulletin* 24.
- Gough, L.H. and Storey, G. (1914):** Methods for the destruction of pink bollworm in cotton seed. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, No. 3.
- Guirguis, M.W.; El-Feshawi, A.A.; Watson, W.M. and Nassef, M.A. (1991):** Occurrence and seasonal abundance of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) infesting cotton. *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 69:63–72.
- Guirguis, M.W.; El-Feshawi, A.A.; Watson, W.M. and Nassef, M.A. (1992):** Studies on the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). IV. Control by burying the infested cotton bolls. *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 70:519–525.
- Guirguis, M.W.; Watson, M.W. and Khalil, F.A. (1976– 1977):** Efficiency of various insecticides in controlling the three cotton bollworms *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.), *Earias insulana* (Boid.) and *Heliothis armigera* Hbn., in Egypt. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*, 10:145–152.
- Hamed-Amin, A.A.; Socar, A.L. and Foda, M.E. (1999):** Predicting the seasonal activity of bollworms *Pectinophora gossypiella* and *Earias insulana* using statistical models in Beheira Governorate. *Zagazig Journal of Agricultural Research (Egypt)*, 26:1429–1439.
- Hamid, A.M. and Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1994):** Effect of half dose insecticide applications on pink bollworm trap catches, green boll infestations and larval storage. *Abstract, Proc. Crop Health Conf.*, 21-24 March, Fayoum, Egypt: 62.
- Hamid, A.M. and Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1995):** Mass-trapping technique for pink bollworm control. *Proc. of 1st Int. Conf. of Pest Control*, Mansoura, Egypt, 3-5 Sept: 189-195.
- Hamid, A.M.; Al-Beltagy, A.M. and El-Hamaky, M.A. (1994):** Influence of certain weather conditions on the bollworms at El-Mansoura District. *J. Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ.*, 19 (2): 815-822.
- Hamid, A.M.; Hober, F.; Al-Beltagy, A.M. and Moawad, G.M. (1996):** Effect of pheromone trap type, location and position on pink bollworm trap catches and its daily variations. *J. Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ.*, 21 (8): 2997-3002.
- Hamid, Z.H.A.; El-Saadany, G.B.; El-Fateh, R.S.M. and Romeilah, M.A. (1999):** Effect of transplanting and planting dates of cotton and the infestation levels of pink and spiny bollworms. *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 77:611–630.
- Hancock, H.A. (1939):** The cottons of Egypt. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, *Bulletin* 235.
- Hancock, H.A. (1944):** The pink bollworm situation in Egypt. *Acco Press*, 22(1):11.
- Hassan, A.G.; Hassanein, M.H. and Kamel, A.A.M. (1963):** The effect of newer chlorinated hydrocarbon insecticides on the bollworms. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt*, 46:31–43.
- Hassan, S.M.; Saad, A.S. and Mansour, M.H. (1974–1975):** Effect of certain insecticides on some cotton pests and on cotton plants. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*, 8:221–226.
- Hassanein, M.H. and Galal, A. (1970):** Studies on the diapause of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella*

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- (Saund.). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 53:69–78.
- Hassanein, M.H.; El-Sebae, A.H.; Khalil, F.M. and ElNaby, A.A. (1971):** The effectiveness of certain insecticides on the boll worms in upper Egypt. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 5:135–143.
- Hassanein, M.H.; Hafez, M. and Rizk, G.A.M. (1970a):** Effectiveness of certain organic insecticides on the population density of boll worms in Upper Egypt (Lepidoptera). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 4:227–236.
- Hassanein, M.H.; Hafez, M. and Rizk, G.A.M. (1970b):** The susceptibility of certain cotton varieties to bollworms infestation. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 53:261–269.
- Hassanein, M.H.; Zaki, M.M. and Kamel, A.A.M. (1968a):** Effect of eight insecticides and certain weather factors on the population density of the cotton bollworms. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 2:161–180.
- Hassanein, M.H.; Zaki, M.M. and Kamel, A.A.M. (1968b):** Toxicological studies on the effect of certain insecticides on cotton bollworms. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series 2:33– 47.
- Hegab, M.E. and Zaki, A.A. (2012):** Toxicological and biological effects of bacteria, *Bacillus thuringiensis* Kurstaki on *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.), and entomopathogenic fungi, *Beauveria bassiana* on *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 3(3): 289 – 297
- Hegab, M.E.; Zaki, A.A.; El-Sayed, A.A. and Amer, A.E. (2020):** Impact of certain insecticides against pink bollworm (*Pectinophora gossypiella*), sucking pests and their associated predators in cotton fields. Serian Journal of Agricultural Searches, 7(3): 467-479.
- Heneidy; A.H.; Khidr, A.A.; Matar, A.M.; Abdel-Halim, A.A. and Hegab, M.S. (2004):** Proper timing and number of releases of the egg parasitoid, *Trichogramma evanescens* (West) for controlling the cotton bollworm in Egyptian cotton fields. Egyptian J. Biological Pest Control, 14(1): 15-19. Proceeding of 1st Arab Conference for Applied Biological Pest control, Cairo, Egypt, 5-7 April, 2004.
- Hosny, M.M. (1980):** The control of cotton pests in Egypt. Outlook on Agriculture 10:204–205.
- Hosny, M.M. (1988):** The role of pheromones in the management of pink bollworm infestation in Egyptian cotton fields. Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment, 21:67– 83.
- Hosny, M.M. and Metwally, A.G. (1967):** A new approach to the problem of pink bollworm control in U.A.R. U.A.R. Ministry of Agriculture Technical Bulletin, 1:37–54.
- Hosny, M.M. and Metwally, A.G. (1974):** Stored cotton sticks as a source of pink bollworm infestation [Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae]. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 58:153–161.
- Hosny, M.M.; Khidr, A.A. and Abdeen, S.A. (1991):** Sex pheromone and population dynamics of the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). Zagazig J. Agric. Res., 18 (5): 1599-1603.
- Hosny, M.M.; Saadany, G.; Iss-Hak, R.; Nasr, E.A.; Moawad, G.; Naguib, M.; Khidr, A.A.; Elnagar, S.H.; Campion, D.G.; Critchley, B.R.; Jones, K.; McKinlay, D.J.; McVeigh, L.J. and Topper, C.P. (1983):** Techniques for the control of cotton pests in Egypt to reduce the reliance on chemical pesticides. In 10th International Congress of Plant Protection, Proceedings of a Conference, Brighton, England,

- November 20–25, Plant Protection for Human Welfare, p. 270. Croydon, England: British Crop Protection Council.
- Hughes, F. (1916):** Fumigation of cotton seed by gaseous hydrocyanic acid. *Agricultural Journal Egypt* 5:64.
- Hussain, N.M. (1992):** Biochemical effect of flufenoxuron on pink bollworm larvae *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Journal of Agricultural Research (Al-Azhar University)*, 16:193–201.
- Hussein, M.H. (1978):** Haematological studies on some lepidopterous larvae. In *Proceedings, 4th Conference of Pest Control, September 30–October 3, 1978*, pp. 357–365. Cairo: Ain Shams University Press.
- Hussein, N.M.; El-Hamaky, H.M.A.; Refaei, A.F. and Hegazy, M.A. (1990):** Joint action of certain insecticides, *Bacillus thuringiensis* and their mixtures on the pink bollworm infestation in cotton plantation of Egypt. *Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent*, 55(2a):307–312.
- Hussein, N.M.; Gadallah, A.I.; Tawfik, S.M. and Shalaby, M.A.M. (2002):** Histological and histochemical studies on the midgut of bollworms in relation Vertimic and Neemazal. The First Conf. of The Central Agric. Pesticide Lab., 3-5 Sep.
- Hussein, N.M.; Hewady, M.A.A.; Taher, S.H. and AbdelHafez, A. (1993):** Biological and biochemical effects of pyriproxyfen juvenoid on the pink bollworm larvae *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Journal of Agricultural Research (Al-Azhar University)*, 17:221–233.
- Hussein, N.M.; Mohamed, M.I. and Enan, R.A. (1993):** Effect of pyriproxyfen juvenoid on the esterases, cholinesterase and acetylcholinesterase activities in larvae of *Earias insulana* (Boisd) and *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo)*, 38:755–760.
- Hussien, E.M.; Shazli, K.A.; Sawaf, S.K. and Zaazou, H. (1962):** Some ecological aspects of the life-history of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella*. IV. The effect of temperature, humidity, cooling and population density on the adult longevity and fecundity. *Journal of Agricultural Research (Alexandria)*, 10:79–93.
- Hussien, E.M.K.; Shazli, A.; Sawaf, S.K. and Zaazou, H. (1961):** Some ecological aspects of the life-history of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). I. The effect of temperature and humidity on the egg stage. II. The effect of temperature and humidity on the larval and pupal stages. *Journal of Agricultural Research (Alexandria)*, 9:177–201.
- Ibrahim, M.M. (2001):** The delayed effect of certain insect growth regulators (IGRS) on the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). *Minufiya J. Agric. Res.*, 26 (3):731-745.
- Ibrahim, M.M.; Abdel-Rahman, Kh.A. and Awad, H.A. (2000):** Evaluation of nine insecticides against the injurious insect-pests of cotton plants in EL-Beheira Governorate. *Adv. Agric. Res.*, 5(1): 1263-1278.
- Ibrahim, S.A. (1997):** Approaches for the integrated control of some cotton pests (Minia region, Egypt). In P. Dugger and D.A. Richter, eds., *Proceedings, Beltwide Cotton Conferences*, pp. 1106–1109. Memphis, Tennessee: National Cotton Council.
- Ibrahim, S.A. and Younis, A.M. (1990):** Insecticidal potency of certain synthetic pyrethroids and organophosphates against the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) and the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd). *Journal of Agricultural Research (Minia University)*, 12:2203–2214.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Isa, A.M.; Fryxell, K.J.; Salama, M.S. and Abu-ElMagd, A.A. (1998a):** Detection of the notch gene in *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). *Journal of the Egyptian German Society of Zoology*, 27(E):231–242.
- Isa, A.M.; Fryxell, K.J.; Salama, M.S. and Abu-ElMagd, A.A. (1998b):** The pink bollworm notch (Potch) is highly homologous with the *Drosophila* notch. *Journal of the Egyptian German Society of Zoology*, 27(E):243–254.
- Johnstone, D.R. (1982a):** Physical and meteorological factors affecting aerial application of sex pheromone for control of the pink bollworm of cotton in Egypt. *Agricultural Meteorology*, 26:117–126.
- Johnstone, D.R. (1982b):** Factors affecting aerial application of a micro encapsulated pheromone formulation for the control of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) by communication disruption on cotton in Egypt. Center Overseas Pest Research, Miscellaneous Report 56.
- Kamal, M. (1935):** Recent advances in the control of the pink boll worm (*Platyedra gossypiella*) by natural enemies. In *Proceedings, 6th International Congress Entomology, Madrid*, 567–581.
- Kamal, M. (1936):** Recent advances in the control of the pink boll-worm (*Platyedra gossypiella* (Saunders)) by natural enemies. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt*, 20:259–271.
- Kamal, M. (1951):** Biological control projects in Egypt, with a list of introduced parasites and predators. *Bulletin Soc. Fouad Ler. Entomol.*, 35:205–220.
- Kambe, T. (1928):** On collecting experiments with the pink bollworm by the purple light trap [in Japanese]. *Korean Agricultural Experiment Station, Annual Report*, 3:260–269.
- Kambe, T. (1931):** Preliminary notes on some hymenopterous parasites of the pink bollworm [in Japanese]. *Korean Agricultural Experiment Station, Annual Report*, 5:221–222.
- Kamel, A.A.M., and Soheb, A. (1960):** Further studies on the effect of some new organo-phosphorus compounds on the cotton leafworm, and cotton bollworms. *Egypt Cotton Gazette*, 39:19–24.
- Kamel, K.; El-Said, A. and Shaarawi, F. (1994):** Ultrastructure of the midgut epithelial cells in the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). *Journal of Tropical Medicine (Cairo)*, 3:189–206.
- Kamel, K.E. (2000):** Ultrastructural and immunocytochemical studies of the midgut endocrine cells of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). *Journal of the Egyptian German Society of Zoology*, 31(E):153–166.
- Kandil, M.A.; Adly, A.M.; Ahmed, A.F. and Shalaby, M.A.M. (2018):** Evaluation of the biological parameters of the interaction the parasitoid, *Bracon brevicornis* Wesmael (Braconidae: Hymenoptera) vs. four different hosts under the no-choice situation. *Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci. (F. Toxicology and Pest control)*, 10(2):133-142.
- Kandil, M.A.; El-Shennawy, R.M. and Ahmed, D.A. (2020):** Carbohydrate hydrolyzing enzymes as a target for pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) control agents. *J. of Plant Protection and Pathology, Mansoura Univ.*, 11(10): 493-499.
- Kansouh, A.S.H.; Afifi, F.A.; Hosny, M.M. and Khalid, R.A. (1976–1977):** The persistence and degradation of Dursban 81 and Nuvacron on cotton plants, in relation to variations in temperature and humidity. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*, 10:217–228.
- Kassem, S.M.I.; Aly, M.I.; Bakry, N.S. and Zeid, M.I. (1986):** Efficacy of

- methomyl and its mixtures against the Egyptian cotton leafworm and bollworms. *Journal of Agricultural Research (Alexandria)*, 31:291–300.
- Keddis, M.E.; Abdel-Sattar, M.M.; Issa, Y.H. and ElGuindy, M.A. (1986):** The toxicity of certain insecticide mixtures to *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*, 14:251–254.
- Khalifa, A. (1967):** Observations on the first stage larva of the pink bollworm. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 60:276.
- Khalifa, A. (1968a):** Effect of treating cotton seed with dieldrin, abavit B, and aldrin on the emergence of pink bollworm moths. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 61:332–334.
- Khalifa, A. (1968b):** The incidence of diapause. In *Pectinophora gossypiella* in the Gezira Scheme, Sudan. *Proceedings of the Royal Entomological Society of London A.*, 43:178–182.
- Khalifa, A. (1971):** The status of pink bollworm in the Gezira, Sudan, with special reference to variety of cotton and sowing date. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt*, 55:105–123.
- Khalifa, A. (1978):** Cotton (*G. barbadense*) seed dressing against pink bollworm. In *Annual Report of the Gezira Research Station, 1966–1967*, pp. 299–305. Agricultural Research Corporation, Sudan Ministry of Agriculture.
- Khalifa, A. (1978):** Relationship of pink bollworm (*Pectinophora gossypiella*) numbers, cotton (*G. barbadense*) variety and sowing date. In *Annual Report of the Gezira Research Station, 1966–1967*, pp. 288–298. Agricultural Research Corporation, Sudan Ministry of Agriculture.
- Khalifa, A.; Elshaarawy, M.F. and Shehata, S.M. (1975):** Incidence of diapause in pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie* 78:63–66.
- Khalifa, H. (1979):** Breeding for bollworm resistance in cotton *Gossypium hirsutum* L. *Coton et Fibres Tropicales*, 34:309–314.
- Khalifa, A.; El-Shaarawy, M.F.; Metwally, A.G. and Abdel-Hafez, A. (1980):** Determination of natural and artificial infestation with first instar larvae of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund). In *Proceedings, 1st Conference of Plant Protection Research Institute, Cairo, December 13–15*, pp. 1–14. Cairo: EDICA.
- Khalil, F.A.; Watson, W.M. and Guirguis, M.W. (1978– 1979):** Evaluation of dimilin and its combinations with different insecticides against some cotton pests in Egypt. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*, 11:71–76.
- Khalil, F.M. and Gouhar, K. (1972):** Field studies on the control of cotton bollworms. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*, 6:141–144.
- Khalil, F.M. and Rizk, G.A. (1972):** Field tests with insecticides for boll worm control in Upper Egypt. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*. 6:137–140.
- Khalilq, A. and Yousaf, M. (1986):** Effect of weather on the light-trap captures of some insects of cotton. *Journal of Agricultural Research (Pakistan)*, 24:313–319.
- Khdir, A.A.; Rashad, A.M.; Nada, M.A. and Abd El -Hafez, A. (1995):** Prediction of infested green bolls by pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) under climatic factors and insecticides program for controlling cotton pests. *Egypt. J. Appl. Sci.*, 10(10):141-153.
- Khdir, A.A.; Abdeen, S.A.; Hassan, A.I.; Abdel-Halim, A. and Mostafa, A.M. (2004):** Evaluation of some insecticides and their joint action

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- against the American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner) on lettuce vegetable plant, *Lactuca sativa* L. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 19(1):275-283.
- Khidr, A.A.; Abdel-Halim, H.E.; Abo-El-Ghar, E.G.; Matar, A.M. and Abdel-Halim, A.A. (2002):** Development of discriminating monitoring techniques for moths' insecticide resistance in *Pectinophora gossypiella* in cotton. 2nd Inter. Conf., Plant Protection Res. Inst., 472-476.
- Khidr, A.A.; Abdou, M.Z.; Kostandy, S.N. and El-Feel, E.A. (1991):** Seasonal population dynamics of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) as monitored by gossypure traps. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 69:83-88.
- Khidr, A.A.; Desuky, W.M.; El-Sheakh, A.A. and Raslan, S.A. (1996):** Sequential use of some insecticides against cotton bollworms in control trials. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 74(2): 321-332.
- Khidr, A.A.; El-Heneidy, A.H.; Abdel-Halim, A.; Eissa, M.A. and Matar, A.M. (2003):** Comparative studies between the efficiency of the egg parasitoid, *Trichogramma evanescens*, West. and the insecticidal applications against the cotton bollworms in Egyptian cotton fields. The First Int. Egyptian –Romanian Conf., 455-464.
- Khidr, A.A.; El-Sorady, A.E.; El-Shouny, K.E. and El-Feel, E.A. (1989):** Control of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), in Kafr El-Sheikh Governorate (Egypt) by mating disruption using hollow fiber, laminated flake and microencapsulated formulation of synthetic pheromone. The 7th Arab Pesticides Conf., Tanta Univ., 12-23.
- Khidr, A.A.; Hassan, A.I.; El-Nemaky, I.H.; Nada, M.S.; Khidr, A.A. and Taman, A.A. (2012):** Evaluating the toxicity and latent effect of Spinosad against different instar Larvae of the American bollworm, *Helicoverpa aemigera* (Hubner). J. Biol. Chem. Environ. Sci., 7(1): 177-188.
- Khidr, A.A.; Kostandy, S.N.; Abbas, M.G.; El-Kordy, M.W. and El-Gougary, O.A. (1990):** Host plants, others than cotton, for the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* and the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana*. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 68: 135-139.
- Khidr, A.A.; Moawad, G.M. and Mc-Veigh, L.J. (1984):** Sex pheromones of Lepidoptera: The effect of control measure using pheromones and insecticides in cotton fields on trap catch of adult male pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Al-Azhar J. Agric. Res., 1: 106-112.
- Khidr, A.A.; Moawad, G.M.; Desuky, W.H.; El-Sheakh, A.A. and Raslan, S.A. (1996):** Effect of some synthetic pyrethroids on bollworm larvae in cotton fields. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 47(1): 123-133.
- Khidr, A.A.; Rashad, A.M.; Nada, M.A. and Abdel-Hafez, A. (1995):** Prediction of infested green cotton bolls by pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) under climatic factors and insecticides program for controlling cotton pests. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 10 (10): 141-153.
- Korkor, A.A.; Hamid, A.M. and Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1998):** Effect of six different local inorganic products on the population density of some cotton pests. Alex. Sci. Exch., 19 (4): 559 – 570.
- Kostandy, S.N.; Khidr, A.A.; Morsi, M.A. and Abdel-Aal, A.A. (1992):** Comparison between cost of pheromone and recommended insecticide applications to control the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) in Egypt during 1988. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 70(4): 1077-1085.
- Kostandy, S.N.; Nada, M.A. and Rashad, A.M. (1998):** Delay appearance of green cotton bolls in

- relation pink bollworm infestation. Arab Univ. J. Agric. Sci. 6(2):561-578.
- Ibrahim, M.M. (2001a):** Side effect of using certain pink bollworm, *pectionphora gossypiella* (Saund.) Sex pheromone formulations and insecticides on some non-target insects. Minufiya j. Agric. Res., 26(3): 715-729.
- Massoud, M.A.; Ibrahim, M.M.; Shekeban, M.M. and Tadros, H.M. (2009):** Effect of three insecticides and two insecticide alternatives on the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) and quality of cotton yield. Alex. J. Agric. Res., 54(1): 155-163.
- Massoud, M.A.; Ibrahim, M.M.; Shekeban, M.M. and Ebeid, H.M. (2009):** Effect of three insecticides and two insecticide Alternatives on the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (saund.) and quality of cotton yield. Alex. J. Agric. Res. 54(1): 155-163
- Massoud, M.A.; Shekeban, M.M.; Saad, A.S.; Mourad, A.K. and Meharb, S.R. (2011).** Cytotoxic effect of potential pesticides on the cerebral neurosecretory cells (CNSC) of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Resistant Pest Management Newsletter, 20(2): 34-39.
- Massoud, M.A.; Zaghloul, O.A.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Shekeban, M.M.; Kordy, A.M. and Mohareb, S.R. (2017):** Heat units Applications for Forcasting of Emergence and Population of Different Developmental Stages of The Pink Bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). J. Adv. Agric. Res. (Fac. Agric. Saba Basha), 22(2): 230-242.
- Matar, A.M. (2003):** Comparison between some biocide and pheromone application for bollworms control on cotton in Egypt. The First Int. Egyptian-Romanina Conf., Zagazig, Dec. 6-8th, 2003 (479-490).
- Matar, A.M. and Azzam, C.R. (2012):** Effect of emamectin benzoate on enzymatic activity and protein banding patterns in laboratory and field strains of the American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner). Annals of Agricultural Science, special issue, March, 68(1): 533- 541.
- Matar, A.M.; Hussein, A.M.; El-Sayed, A.A. and Kandil, M.A. (2018):** Effect of Magnetic Power and Radiant Compound on Some Biological and Biochemical Aspects of *Earias insulana* (Boisduval) (Lep.: Noctuidae). Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 11(6):85– 94.
- Matar, A.M.; Khidr, A.A.; Abd-Elkarim, H.E.; Abd-Elghar, E.G. and Abd-Elhalim, A.A. (2003):** Development of discriminating techniques for moths' insecticides resistance in *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidas) in cotton. Eight Arab Congress of Plant Protection, 12-16 October 2003, El-Beida, Libya (Abstract Book, 80-E).
- McKillop, A.T. (1913):** On the conversion of cotton sticks into charcoal for the destruction of the Pink Bollworm. Agricultural Journal Egypt, 3:127.
- McVeigh, L.J.; Critchley, B.R. and Campion, D.G. (1983):** Control of the pink bollworm in Egypt by mating disruption using pheromones. In 10th International Congress of Plant Protection, Proceedings of a Conference, Brighton, England, November 20–25, Plant Protection for Human Welfare, p. 268. Croydon, England: British Crop Protection Council.
- Megahed, M.M.; Ammar, D.; Metwally, A.G. and Rashad, A. (1982):** Studies on the attraction of males of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders), in Egypt, to the sex pheromone 'gossyplure'. Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 60:181–199.
- Meguid, M.A.; Ahmed, M.M.; Ragab, M.G. and Zidan, L.T. (2003):** Ovicidal and larvicidal activities of two insecticides against some cotton insect

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- pests. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 19(10): 366-373.
- Mesbah, H.A.; Abd El-Rahman, Kh.A.; EL-Naggar, A.Z.; Massoud, M.A. and Tadros, H.M. (2014):** Effect of certain ecological and agro techniques on the incidence of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) and spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana*, (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) on cotton plants. Alex. Sci. Ex. J., 35(1): 29 – 38.
- Mesbah, H.A.; El-Naggar, A.Z.; Abdel-Mageed, A.A. and Abouzaid, H.M. (2020):** New approaches for controlling pink and spiny bollworms through pattern of bio control agents and chemicals on cotton properties. J. Adv. Agric. Res., 25(2):228-245.
- Mesbah, H.A.; Ibrahim, M.M.; Awad, H.A. and El-Naggar, A.Z. (2004):** Performance of plant nutrients and alternative chemicals against the cotton bollworms: *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lep.: Gelechiidae) and *Earias insulana* (Lep.: Noctuidae), at El-Beheira Governorate. Adv. Agric. Res., 9(3): 689-706.
- Mesbah, H.A.; Ibrahim, M.M.; Saad, A.S.; Awad, H.A. and Abd El-Rahman, Kh.A. (2000):** Effect of four-sex pheromone for mutations on the infestation with the pink bollworm, *pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) and yield characteristics of cotton plants. j. Adv. Agric. Res., 5 (2): 1279-1290.
- Mesbah, H.A.; Ibrahim, M.M.; Tayeb, E.H.; El-Nagar, A.Z. And El-Nimr, H.M. (2000):** Plant health, a new approach for the attainment of tolerant plants to pests' infestation. (5) Effect of fertilization and foliar application of nutritive elements on the infestation of cotton with bollworms. J. Adv. Agric. Res., 5 (2): 1437-1456.
- Mesbah, H.A.; Ibrahim, M.M.; Tayeb, E.H.; EL-Naggar, A.Z. and EL-Nimr, H.M. (2000):** Plant health, a new approach for the attainment of tolerant plants to pests' infestation. (5): Effect of fertilization and foliar application of nutritive elements on the infestation of cotton with bollworms. Adv. Agric. Res., 5(2): 1437-1454.
- Mesbah, H.A.; Abdel-Rahman, Kh.A.; EL-Naggar, A.Z. and Mabrouk, A.A. (2009):** New approach for evaluating the use of foliar fertilizers, alternative chemical compounds and release of *Trichogramma evanescens* in an integrated pest management for controlling pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in organic and conventional cotton plants. Minufiya J. Agric. Res., 34(1):253-267.
- Mesbah, H.A.; Tayeb, E.H.; EL-Naggar, A.Z. and EL-Shahat, M.S. (2007):** The relative efficiency of pesticides and fertilizers on cotton crop. I. Interaction effects of fertilizer type and some insecticides on bollworms infestation and cotton quality. J. Adv. Agric. Res., 12 (1): 115 - 126.
- Metwally, A.G. and Hosny, M.M. (1972a):** Factors affecting the resting stage duration of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 50:21–24.
- Metwally, A.G. and Hosny, M.M. (1972b):** On the initiation and termination of the pink bollworm diapause *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 50:17–20.
- Metwally, A.G. and Hosny, M.M. (1972c):** Temperature and relative humidity as factors influencing the termination of diapause in the pink bollworm. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 55:373–377.
- Metwally, A.G. and Hosny, M.M. (1974a):** The approximate flight-range of pink bollworm moths and the rate of infestation at cardinal directions around villages [Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae].

- Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 58:55–64.
- Metwally, A.G. and Hosny, M.M. (1974b):** The perpendicular distribution of pink bollworm infestation at different levels of the cotton plant [Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae]. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 58:89–92.
- Metwally, A.G.; Abdel-Hafez, A. and El-Bishry, H. (1976):** The use of pheromone traps as a survey tool for *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 54:9–15.
- Metwally, A.G.; Abdel-Hafez, A.; Khalifa, A. and ElShaarawy, M.F. (1980):** Breeding pink bollworm on different host plants. In Proceedings, 1st Conference of Plant Protection Research Institute, Cairo, December 13–15, pp. 15–32. Cairo: EDICA.
- Metwally, A.G.; El-Lakwah, F.A.; Shalaby, F.F. and El-Gemeiy, H.M. (1983):** Natural role of diseases against the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) in Egyptian cotton fields. Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 61:1–21.
- Metwally, A.G.; Megahed, M.M.; Ammar, E.D. and Rashad, A. (1982):** Effect of the sex pheromone 'gossypure' on suppression of field populations of *Pectinophora gossypiella* in Egypt. Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 60:209–223.
- Metwally, E.M.; El-Ghonamy, A.I.; Moawad, G.M.; Raslan, S.A. and Desuky, W.M.H. (1996):** Heat unit and weather factors in relation to prediction of the pink bollworm infestation. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 74:939–955.
- Metwally, S.M.; El-Khodary, A.S. and El-Zanan, A.A. (1979):** Seasonal fluctuations of the major cotton pest's population and their predaceous insects at Kafr El-Sheikh Province. J. Agric. Res., Tanta Univ., 5(1): 300-308
- Moawad, G.; Khidr, A.A.; Zaki, M.; Critchley, B.R.; Mcveigh, L.J. and Campion, D.G. (1991):** Large-scale use of hollow fibre and microencapsulated pink bollworm pheromone formulations integrated with conventional insecticides for the control of the cotton pest complex in Egypt. Tropical Pest Management, 37:10–16.
- Moawad, G.M. (1981):** Survival of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) under various soils and climatic conditions. Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 59:99–105.
- Moawad, G.M. and Hussein, A.H.M. (1980):** Effect of certain agricultural practices on the population density of the overwintering pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* larvae. Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 58:265–276.
- Moawad, G.M. and Khidr, A.A. (1982):** The influence of juvenile hormone on the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Agric. Res. Rev., 60(1): 225-235.
- Moawad, G.M.; Bekheit, H.K.M.; Gomaa, E.A. and Ashour, M.B. (1994a):** Integrated use of pheromone and conventional insecticides against pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo) Special Issue:1025–1044.
- Moawad, G.M.; Bekheit, H.K.M.; Gomaa, E.A. and Ashour, M.B. (1994b):** Mating disruption trials for the control of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella*. Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo) Special Issue:1059–1073.
- Moawad, G.M.; El-Hamaky, M.A.; Gergis, M.F. and Sawires, Z.R. (1991):** The impact of sex pheromones and insecticides on cotton piercing sucking pests in Middle Egypt. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 19:231–236.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Moawad, G.M.; El-Shaeady, A.A.; Rashad, A.M.; Shalaby, M.A.M. and Gadallah, A.I. (1990):** Suppression of pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) infestation in cotton fields treated with sex pheromones. *Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo) Special Issue*:531–543.
- Moawad, G.M.; Hamed-Amin, A.A. and Hossain, A.M. (1994):** Spatial distribution of two cotton bollworms *Pectinophora gossypiella* and *Earias insulana* in Fayoum, Egypt. *Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo)*, 39:805–813.
- Moawad, G.M.; Khidr, A.A.; Zaki, M.; Critchley, B.R.; Mc-Veigh, L.J. and Champion, D.G. (1991):** Large-scale use of hollow fiber and microencapsulated pink bollworm pheromone formulations integrated with conventional insecticides for the control of the cotton pest complex in Egypt. *Tropical Pest Management*, 37(1): 10-16.
- Moawad, G.M.; Rashad, A.M.; Shalaby, M.A.M. and Gadallah, A.I. (1990):** Effect of some insect growth regulators on the larvae of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (S) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*, 18:149–155.
- Moawad, G.M.; Raslan, S.A.A. and Desuky, W.M.H. (1996):** Integrated control of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 74:981–998.
- Moawad, G.M.; S.A.A. Raslan, W.M.H. Desuky, E.M. Metwally, and Ibrahim, A.E. (1996):** New approach for pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) control in Egypt using fatal attraction. *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 74:957–972.
- Moawad, G.M.; Sawires, Z.R.; El-Hamaky, M.A. and Gergis, M.F. (1991):** The impact of sex pheromones and insecticides on the natural enemies in cotton fields in Middle Egypt. *Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series*, 19:237–242.
- Moawad, G.M.; Sawires, Z.R.; Watson, M.W. and Gaber, A.E. (1994):** Male disruption pheromone as a new strategy in controlling pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) in Egypt. In D.J. Herber and D.A. Richter, eds., *Proceedings, Beltwide Cotton Conferences*, pp. 1035–1038. Memphis, Tennessee: National Cotton Council.
- Moftah, E.A.; Khidr, A.A.; Abdeen, S.A. and El-Hamaky, M.A. (1990):** Relative susceptibility of the American bollworm, *Heliothis armigera* (Hübner.) to some commercial products of *Bacillus thuringiensis* and their latent effect. *Minia J. Agric. Res. and Dev.*, 12(2): 795-807.
- Moftah, E.A.; Younis, A.M.; Gergis, M.F. and Khidr, A.A. (1988):** Thermal requirements and prediction models for pink bollworm (PBW) *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Journal of Agricultural Research (Minia University)*, 10:1563–1573.
- Moftah, E.A.; Younis, A.M.; Gergis, M.F. and Khidr, A.A. (1988):** Thermal requirements and prediction models for pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). *Minia. J. Agric. Res. and Dev.*, 10(4): 1563-1573.
- Mohamed, M.I.; Anan, R.A.; Hussein, N.M. and Moustafa, Z.K. (1993):** Some dehydrogenase enzymes affected by juvenoid materials in *Earias insulana* and *Pectinophora gossypiella* larvae. *Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo)*, 38:747–753.
- Monsarrat, A.; Abol-Ela, S.; Abdel-Hamid, I.; Fediere, G.; Kuhl, G.; El-Husseini, M. and Giannotti, J. (1995):** A new RNA picorna-like virus in the cotton pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Lep.: Gelechiidae) in Egypt. *Entomophaga*, 40:47–54.

- Mostafa, A.M.; Al-Beltagy, A.M. and El-Khawalka, M. H. (1994):** Effect of the predator *Orius* sp. on the population densities of common red spider mite *Tetranychus* spp. under pheromone and insecticide application in cotton field. Zagazig J. Agric. Res., 1 (6): 1797 – 1805.
- Mostafa, Z.K.; El-Sherif, L.S. and Hewady, M.A.A. (1995):** Effect of certain volatile plant oils on the activity of malate dehydrogenase and malic enzyme In *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) and *Earias insulana* (Boisd) larvae (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Journal of the Egyptian German Society of Zoology, 17(E):13–23.
- Mourad, M.A. (1993):** Effect of some insecticidal treatments on flowering, shedding, bollworm infestation, and yield of Giza 70 cotton variety (*Gossypium barbadense*). Journal of Agricultural Research (Tanta University), 19:718–728.
- Mourad, M.A.; Omar, M.E. and Mahran, A.A. (1991a):** Field potency of different insecticides against cotton boll worms. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 69:57–62.
- Mourad, M.A.; Omar, M.E. and Mahran, A.A. (1991b):** Alternate use of insecticides against the cotton bollworms *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* Boisd. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 69:99–106.
- Moursy, E.B. (1992):** Changes in protein, nucleic acids and glycogen during embryonic development in the eggs of active and overwintered moths of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Bulletin of the Faculty of Agriculture (University of Cairo), 43:527–537.
- Moursy, E.B. and Bartlett, A.C. (1991):** Effect of ‘pyriproxyfen’ as juvenile hormone analogue on the reproductive potentiality of the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 19:191–197.
- Moustafa, A.A.; Abd El-Hafez, A.; Afifi, A.S.; Amin, T.R. and Ahmed, D.A. (2001):** Biochemical effects of some citrus essential oils on pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). First Conference of Role of Biochemistry in Environment and Agriculture Feb. 6-8/2001, Biochemistry Dept. Faculty of Agric. Cairo Univ. Giza, Egypt.
- Moustafa, H.Z.; Kandil, M.A. and El-Bassouiny, H.M. (2021):** Genetic profile characterization of *Earias insulana* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) in EGYPT. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4(2): 341–351.
- Nada, M.A. (1996a):** Effect of some insecticides on susceptible and field strains of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) at Sharkia and Fayoum Governorates. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 11 (5):356-361.
- Nada, M.A. (1996b):** The interaction relationship between population of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders), and the cotton fruiting structures receptors. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 16(3): 307-318.
- Nada, M.A. (2000):** The triangular relationship between the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) infestation cotton planting date and squares occurrence. Zagazig J. Agric. Res., 27: 1469-1479.
- Nada, M.A. and Abdel-Azem, E.M. (2005):** Effect of two types of entomopathogenic fungi, *Paeceiomces violacea* and *Paeceiomces varioti* on biological aspects of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 20 (12B): 691-698.
- Nada, M.A. and Ragab, M.G. (2010):** Prediction of American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hüb.), depending on accumulated heat units in cotton fields. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 1(4):195-208.
- Nada, M.A.; Abou-Setta, M.M.; El-Sayed, A.A.; Ragab, M.G. and**

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Hassanein, M.K. (2018):** Effect of climate changes on growth pattern of cotton plants in relation to the infestation with pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) in Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 96(1):1-14.
- Nada, M.A.; Abou-Setta, M.M.; Elsherbeny, A.M. and Ragab, M.G. (2002):** Using fruiting structures of cotton plants in predicting *Peclinophom gossypiella* first generation construction. 2nd International Conference, Plant Protection Research Institute, Cairo, Egypt, 21-24 Dec., 1: 477-481.
- Nada, M.A.; Abou-Setta, M.N.; El-Sherbiny, A.H. and Ragab, M.G. (2009):** Prediction of cotton yield depending on growing date and period of bollworms control. Egypt J. Agric Res., 87 (2):489-497.
- Nada, M.A.; Hewady, M.A. and Rashad, A.M. (1994):** Effectiveness of the parasitic mite, *Pyemotes herfsi* (Oudemans) on diapausing larvae of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Egypt. J. Biol. Pest control, 4(1): 17-23.
- Nada, M.A.; Hewady, M.A. and Rashad, A.M. (1995):** Releasing of ectoparasitic mite, *Pyemotes herfsi* (Oudemans) into cotton stalks and its effect on population of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Egypt. J. Biol. Pest control, 5(2): 91-93.
- Nada, M.A.; Kostandy, S.N. and Rashad, A.M. (1998):** Sampling technique for recording the population trends of pink bollworm in cotton fields. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, 76:1-7.
- Nada, M.A.; Ragab, M.G. and Amer, A.E. (2009):** Effectiveness of accumulated heat units on population fluctuation of spiny bollworm and associated predators in cotton and maze fields. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 87 (4): 1009-1023.
- Nada, M.A.; Ragab, M.G. and El-Lebody, K.A. (2010):** Occurrence and movements of the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) within some of its host plants. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 1(1):635-646.
- Nada, M.A.; Ragab, M.G. and Mansour, E.S. (2004):** Seasonal abundance and prediction possibility of American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hub.) in relation to pheromone trap catches and heat unit accumulations. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 19(11): 394-409.
- Nada, M.A.; Ragab, M.G. and Zaki, A.A. (2012):** Relationship between lunar light and population of *Helicoverpa armigera* (HÜb.) moths at Gharbia Governorate. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 3(11):1241-1251.
- Nada, M.A.; Watson, W.M. and Ragab, M.G. (2006):** Peaks occurrence of spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) in relation to accumulated heat units. Egypt J. of Appl. Sci., 21 (3): 312-325.
- Nasr, E.A. (1976–1977):** Effect of certain recommended insecticides on the population density of the egg-masses of the cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.), and their efficiency in controlling pink and spiny bollworms. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 10:105–108.
- Nasr, E.A. (1972):** Effect of number of sprays on the rate of bollworm infestation, cotton yield and fibre quality (Lepidoptera). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 6:93–102.
- Nasr, E.A. and Azab, A.K. (1970):** Behavior and activity of the pink and the spiny cotton bollworms, in Egypt. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 53:235– 243.
- Nasr, E.S.A. (1973):** The efficiency of various insecticides in controlling the two cotton bollworms *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* Boisd. (Lepidoptera). Bulletin

- of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 7:1–13.
- Nasr, E.S.A. and Azab, A.K. (1970):** Susceptibility of different cotton varieties to bollworms infestation. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 53:459–472.
- Nassef, A.M.; Ragab, M.G. and Khattab, M.A. (2009):** Influence of cowpea intercropping with cotton on population density of certain insects under three intercropping dates in Garbia Governorate. Egypt J. of Appl. Sci., 24(4B):828-837.
- Nassef, M.A. and Watson, W.M. (1999):** Sequential spray schedules of insecticides to control bollworms as target pests in addition to certain sap suckers as non-target pests in cotton fields. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 77:1155–1162.
- Nassef, M.A.; Hamed, A.M. and Watson, W.M. (1999):** Mass-trapping of pink bollworm with gossyplure. Journal of Agricultural Research (Alexandria), 44:327–334.
- Nasser, M.A.; Abdel-Fattah, S.A.; El-Bahrawi, A. and Ellabany. M. (1978):** Activity of synthetic pyrethroids and certain insecticides on cotton boll worms in relation to their effect on fiber quality in Egypt. Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijksuniversiteit Gent, 43:719–725.
- Omar, H.I.H.; Haydar, M.F. and El-Sorady, A.E.M. (1994):** Effect of sowing date of intercropping cowpea with cotton on infestation with some major pests. Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 72:691–698.
- Omar, M.E.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; El-Feel, E.A. and Mesbah, H. (1992):** Control of *Spodoptera littoralis* larvae with some insecticides in combination with *Bacillus thuringiensis*. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 7 (4): 62-70.
- Omar, M.H. (1980):** Meteorological factors affecting the epidemiology of the cotton leaf worm and the pink bollworm. World Meteorological Organization, Technical Note 167.
- Omara, Sh.M. and El-Sayed, A.A. (1999):** Effect of two different neemazal formulations on spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) infesting cotton plants at Khattara region, Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. Zagazig J. Agric. Res., 26(6): 1751-1762.
- Ragab, M.G.; Abd El-Dayem, H.M. and liashcm, H.H.A. (2004):** Histopathological and biochemical effects of some plant extracts on *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hub.) larvae. Egypt J. Appl. Sci., 19(12A): 285-296.
- Ragab, M.G.; Abdel-Gawad, H.A. and Kostandy, S.N. (2009):** The correlation between the predatory insects and the cotton bollworms in untreated cotton fields at Gharbia Governorate. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, 86: 149-160.
- Ragab, M.G.; Allam, S.A. and Farghali, A.A. (2004):** Effect of three IGR's compounds on some biological aspects of *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner). Minufiya J. Agric. Res., 29 (5): 1195-1206.
- Ragab, M.G.; Eldewy, M.E. and Zedan, L.T. (2010):** Occurrence and seasonal abundance of the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) infesting cotton in the north Delta. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 1(5):459-471.
- Ragab, M.G.; El-Sayed, A.A. and Nada, M.A. (2014):** The Effect of some biotic and a biotic environmental factors on Seasonal fluctuations of *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hub.). Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 92(1):101-119.
- Ragab, M.G.; El-Zoghby, A.A. and Attala, F.A. (2007):** Percentage of parasitism among the American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) infesting cotton plants in Gharbia Governorate. Annals of Agric. Sc. Moshtohor, 45(4):1717-1723.
- Ragab, M.G.; Salem, H.A. and El-Shershaby, M.M. (2004):** Investigation of different sowing dates

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- and different weather factors on the infestation of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). J. Egypt. Acad. Soc. Environ. Develop. (A- Entomology), 5(1): 69-81.
- Rashad, A.M. and Kostandy, S.N. (1993):** Effect of bollworms crowding on the insect development. Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo), 38:319–325.
- Rashad, A.M.; Kostandy, S.N. and Naguib, S.M. (1992):** Mating studies on pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 70:11–18.
- Rashad, A.M.; Nada, M.A. and Abdel-Salam, N.M. (1993):** Effect of some factors on diapausing larvae and emerging moths of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 8(1): 488-500.
- Rashad, A.M.; Nada, M.A.; Bekheit, H.K. and Abd El -Hafez, A. (1995):** Prediction of overwintering pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) diapausing larvae depended on diapause stage at the previous end cotton season. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 10(4):166-172.
- Raslan, S.A.; Aioub, A.A. and Hegab, M.E. and Hassanein, S.E. (2003):** Field evaluation of some insecticides against pink and spiny bollworms on cotton plants. Agric. Res. J., Suez-Canal Univ., 2(1):95-106.
- Raslan, S.A.; Desuky, W.M.; Amer, A.E. and El-Sayed, A.A. (2009):** Efficiency of natural product emamectin benzoate against cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) and pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 87 (4): 999-1008.
- Rasmy, A.H. (1971):** Effect of chemical control on the cotton bollworm on population of spider mites in cotton (Acarinae). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 5:79–83.
- Rizk, G.A.M. and Radwan, H.S.A. (1975a):** Response of pink bollworm to soil application of two unique growth disruptions. In Proceedings, 8th British Insecticide and Fungicide Conference, November 17–20, Brighton, England, pp. 299–303. Croydon, England: British Crop Protection Council.
- Rizk, G.A.M. and Radwan, H.S.A. (1975b):** Potency and residuality of two antimoult compounds against cotton leafworm and bollworms. Zeitschrift fur Angewandte Entomologie, 79:136–140.
- Rizk, M.A. and El-Bermawy, Z.A. (1987):** Field tests of *Bacillus thuringiensis* (β -Endotoxin) and chemical insecticides for control of the cotton leafworm and cotton bollworm on cotton. Journal of Agricultural Research (Minia University), 9:269–286.
- Rizk, M.A.; Soliman, M.A. and Abdel-Naby, A.A. (1984):** Factors affecting the diapause of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) in Middle Egypt. Assiut Journal of Agricultural Science, 15:285–294.
- Roelofs, W.L. (1978):** Threshold hypothesis for pheromone perception. Journal of Chemical Ecology, 4:685–699.
- Roelofs, W.L. (1981):** Pheromones, plateaus, and plaititudes. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of America 27:3–8. Roelofs, W.L., and A. Comeau. 1970. Lepidopterous sex attractants discovered by field screening tests. Journal of Economic Entomology, 63:969–974.
- Rofail, M.F.; El-Sorady, A.E.M. and Rashad, A.M. (1998):** Comparative cytological studies on a susceptible and resistant strains of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.). Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 76:535–543.
- Rofail, M.F.; Nada, M.A.; El-Sisi, A.G. and Rashad, A.M. (2000):** Time of spraying some natural oils as a limiting

- factor for controlling cotton bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research, 78:1499-1507.
- Rostom, Z.M.F. (1963):** Some observations on nutrition and digestion of the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 46:171–188.
- Rostom, Z.M.F. (1960):** The chemical composition of the larvae of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders), before and during diapause (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 44:421–449.
- Rostom, Z.M.F. (1978):** Weight and specific gravity of the haemolymph in active and diapausing larvae of *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). In Proceedings, 4th Conference of Pest Control, September 30–October 3, 1978, pp. 366–373. Cairo: Ain Shams University Press.
- Rostom, Z.M.F.; Alaauhari, A.M.J. and AbdelFattah, M.M. (1972):** Free amino acids and total protein in the haemolymph of *Pectinophora gossypiella* during induction and termination of diapause. Proceedings of the Egyptian Academy of Science, 25:71.
- Russell, D.A. and Radwan, S.M. (1992):** Modeling the impact of cotton fruiting phenology on pink bollworm population dynamics in Egypt. Series Entomologica (Dordrecht), 49:323–324.
- Russell, D.A. and Radwan, S.M. (1993):** Modelling pink bollworm [*Pectinophora gossypiella*] mating disruption in Egyptian cotton. Bulletin OILB/SROP, 16:268–275.
- Russell, D.A.; Radwan, S.M.; El-Deeb, Y.A. and Mahmoud, H.M. (1995):** Modeling pheromone use for pink bollworm control in Egypt. In G.A. Constable and N.W. Forrester, eds., Challenging the Future: Proceedings of the World Cotton Research Conference-1, pp. 475–479. Melbourne, Australia: CSIRO.
- Saad, A.F.S.A.; Elewa, M.A.; Hauwila, T. and Ibrahim, M.M. (1984):** Synthetic pyrethroids used for cotton pests control as a factor affecting constituents of cotton seeds. Mededelingen Van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen, Rijks
- Saad, A.F.S.A.; El-Sebae, A. and Sharaf, I.M.F.(1981) :**AC 222,705, a broad-spectrum pyrethroid insecticide: Performance in Egypt [summary in French]. In Proceedings, British Crop Protection Conference: Pests and Diseases (11th British Insecticide and Fungicide Conference), November 16–19, Brighton, England, pp. 381–388. Croydon, England: British Crop Protection Council.
- Saad, A.S.; Tayeb, E.H.; Awad, H.A. and El-Bassiuny, H.M. (2012):** The Release of the parasitoides, *Trichogramma evancens* to control the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) and the side effect of certain insecticides on it. Alex. Sci. Ex. J., 33(1): 1-10.
- Salama, A.E.; Ashry, M.A.; Saad, A.S. and Khalil, F. (1979):** Progressive toxicity symptoms in mid-gut epithelia of pink bollworm caused by certain compounds. Journal of Agricultural Research (Tanta University), 5:182–192.
- Salama, H.S. (1983):** Cotton pest management in Egypt. Crop Protection, 2:183–191.
- Salama, H.S. and Foda, M.S. (1984):** Studies on the susceptibility of some cotton pests to various strains of *Bacillus thuringiensis*. Journal of Plant Disease Protection, 91:65–70.
- Salama, H.S. and Tolba, R.A. (1971):** Chemical senses in lepidopterous larvae with reference to gustation and olfaction in *Chilo agamemnon* Bles.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Zeitschrift für Angewandte Entomologie, 67:352–360.
- Salama, M.S. (2000):** The expression of pectinophorin, a haemolymph protein in diapausing pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Journal of the Egyptian German Society of Zoology, 33:379–410.
- Salama, M.S. and Hassan, S.A. (2001):** Developmental proteins during the life cycle of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Journal of the Egyptian German Society of Zoology, 34: 29-40.
- Salama, M.S. and Miller, T.A. (1992):** A diapause associated protein of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Archives of Insect Biochemistry and Physiology, 21:1–11.
- Salama, M.S. and Miller, T.A. (1993):** In vitro translation of diapause messenger RNA from the fat body of active and diapause larvae of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Archives of Insect Biochemistry and Physiology, 23:1–11.
- Salama, M.S.; El-Shafei, A.M. and Abdel-Rahman, H.A. (1992):** Cloning the gene coding for pectinophorin from *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Journal of the Egyptian German Society of Zoology, 7(A):315–327.
- Salama, M.S.; El-Shafei, A.M. and Abdel-Rahman, H.A. (1992):** Hybridization analysis to isolate pectinophorin gene from *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Journal of the Egyptian German Society of Zoology, 7(B):223–237.
- Salama, M.S.; Miller, T.A. and Schouest, Jr. L.P. (1992):** A new test for measuring diapause in the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Life Sciences, 51:411–413
- Salem, A.A.; El-Banby, M.A.; Metwally, A.G. and Abdel-Hafez, A.M. (1989):** Effect of gamma radiation on the pupae of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Journal of Agricultural Research (Minia University), 11:639–659.
- Salem, A.A.; El-Banby, M.A.; Metwally, A.G. and Abdel-Hafez, A.M. (1989):** Mating competitiveness of irradiated male pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Journal of Agricultural Research (Minia University) 11:617–624.
- Salem, A.A.; El-Banby, M.A.; Metwally, A.G. and Abdel-Hafez, A.M. (1989):** Suppression of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders), populations with releases of sterilized moths in field cages. Journal of Agricultural Research (Minia University), 11:625–638.
- Salem, H.A.; Ragab, M.G. and El-Shershaby, M.M. (2004):** Monitoring the triangular relationship between maize, cotton and the infestation of the American bollworm (ABW), *Helicoverpa armigera* (Fib.) and the spiny bollworm (SBW), *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). AI-Azhar J. Agric. Res., 39: 31-35.
- Salem, S.A. (1991):** Response of cotton bollworms, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* Boisd. to see neem kernal pure oil. Annals of Agricultural Science (Moshtohor), 29:597–607.
- Salem, S.A.; Radwan, S.M.E. and Hamaky, M.A. (1990):** Prospects of using sex pheromone for the control of cotton bollworms, *Earias insulana* Boisd. and *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) in cotton fields. Annals of Agricultural Science (Moshtohor), 28:1743–1752.
- Salem, Y.S. and El-Shaarawy, M.F. (1982):** Factors affecting longevity and reproduction capacity of the pink bollworm moths *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) developed from diapaused larvae. II. Effect of larval food. Ain Shams University Research Bulletin 2016.
- Samy, O. (1958):** Green cotton boll shedding in relation to insect infestation

- of flowers. Agricultural Research Review (Cairo), 36:51–58.
- Shaaban, Z.; El-Doksh, H.A. and Al-Beltagy, A.M. (1992):** Tolerance of pink bollworm larvae to insecticides as influenced by two chemical programs. Alex. Sci. Exch., 13 (4): 803-813.
- Shairra, S.A.; El-Sharkawy, M.A.; Hassan, K.A. and Ahmed, D.A. (2016):** The efficacy of entomopathogenic nematodes on the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella*. Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 8(2): 103-113.
- Shaker, N.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991a):** Biochemical studies on diapause of the pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Alex. Sci. Exch., 12 (2): 195-206.
- Shaker, N.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991b):** Integrated control of cotton bollworms by using early sowing and less susceptible cotton cultivars. Alex. Sci. Exch., 12 (4): 761-774.
- Shaker, N.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Taman, F. A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991):** Biochemical studies on diapause of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Alex. Sci. Exch., 12 (2): 195-206.
- Shaker, N.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Taman, F.A. and El-Khishen, S.A. (1991):** Integrated control of cotton bollworms by using early sowing and less susceptible cotton cultivars. Alex. Sci. Exch., 12 (4): 761-774.
- Shalaby, F.F.; Nada, M.A.; Hafez, A.A. and Hassan, K.A. (1998):** Larvae of common green lacewing, *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) preying on *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). First regional symposium for applied biological control in Mediterranean countries, Cairo Egypt, October 25-29: 217-222.
- Shalaby, M.A.M. (2009):** Spermatogenesis of adults, pink and spiny bollworm. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, 86:25-35.
- Shalaby, M.A.M. (2009):** Study on the cellular enclosures of the mid-gut epithelium of spiny and pink bollworms. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, 86: 37–44.
- Shalaby, M.A.M. and Rashad, A.M. (2007):** Aqueous extract of the seed of zanzalakht tree, Meliaceae, *Melia azadirachta* L. as a factor to complement chemical control methods against bollworm infestation. J. Egypt. Acad. Soc. Environ. Develop., 8(2): 11-17.
- Shalaby, M.A.M. and Rashad, A.M. (2009):** Insecticidal, biological and biochemical effects of two oils on *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* (Boisd.). Egyptian J. of Appli. Sci., 24(3 B): 261-272.
- Shalaby, M.A.M.; Adly, A.M. and Ahmed, A.F. (2013):** Study on *Bracon Brevicornis* – Pink bollworm interaction. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, 90:169-182.
- Shalaby, M.A.M; Adly, A.M., and Ahmed, A.F. (2019):** Cow's urine-dung extract foliar spraying as a complementary pest control method against bollworm complex on the cotton plant. International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR). 8(7): 212-219.
- Shazli, A. and Shafik, M.T. (1963):** Succinic dehydrogenase activity in active and dormant larvae of *Platyedra gossypiella* (Saunders). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 46:227–232.
- Shekeban, M.M. (2000):** Studies on insecticides resistance in certain major cotton insects with special reference to different measurements and monitoring methods. Ph.D. Thesis. Menoufiya University.
- Shekeban, M.M. (2002):** Attracticide and biochemical monitoring for insecticide resistance in pink bollworm (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Proc. 1st

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Conf. of the Central Agric. Pestic. Lab. Giza, Egypt, 3-5 September, 2: 607-619.
- Shekeban, M.M. (2002):** Vial residue assay technique and esterases electrophoresis for resistance monitoring in pink bollworm. The 2nd International Conf. Plant Protection Research Institute, Giza, Egypt, 21-24 December, 1: 673-679.
- Shekeban, M.M. (2007):** Joint toxic effect and synergism of pyrethroids as resistance management strategy in pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). Egypt. J. Agric. Rec., 85 (5): 565-1578.
- Shekeban, M.M. (2008):** Situation of pyrethroid resistance in spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana*, (Boisd) and carbaryl joint toxic effect. Resistant Pest Management Newsletter, 17(2): 38-43.
- Shekeban, M.M. (2012):** Evaluation of ten insecticides distributed into seven sequences against bollworm complex. Alex. J. Sci. Ex., 33(4): 261-267
- Shekeban, M.M. and El-Nemaky, I.H. (2010):** Toxicity and latent of certain pyrethroids on pink bollworm. J. Pest Cont. & Environ. Sci., 18(1): 23-36.
- Shekeban, M.M.; Abdel-Rhman, K.A. and El-Bassiony, M.M. (2003a):** The Use of Attracticide Resistance Monitoring Technique to Monitor for Toxicity, Joint toxic effect and Resistance to Some Pyrethroid Insecticides in Pink Bollworm. The 1st Inter. Egyptian-Romanian Conf., Zagazig Univ., December 6-8, pp. 571-582.
- Shekeban, M.M.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Abo El-Amayem, M.M.; Kassem, S.M.; Mancee, A.H. and El-Arami, S.A. (2009):** Monitoring organophosphorous resistance in pink bollworm using the Attracticide Resistance Monitoring Technique. Resistant Pest Management Newsletter, 18(2): 31-36.
- Shekeban, M.M.; El-Bassiony, M.M. and El-Namky, I. (2003):** Monitoring for toxicity, joint toxic effect and resistance to deltamethrin, fenpropathrin and thiodicarb insecticides in pink bollworm. The 1st Inter. Egyptian-Romanian Conf., Zagazig Univ., December 6-8, 2003, 561-570.
- Shekeban, M.M.; El-Bassiony, M.M. and El-Namky, I. (2004):** Toxicity, joint toxic effect and resistance Monitoring to cypermethrin, alpha-cypermethrin and thiodicarb in pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). J. Pest Control & Environ. Sci.;12 (1/2): 1-12.
- Shekeban, M.M.; El-Namky, I. and Ibrahim, M.M. (2005):** Synergised cypermethrin and α -cypermethrin as resistance management strategy in pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders). J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 30 (3): 1647 – 1654.
- Shekeban, M.M.; Saad, A.S.; Zaher, M.A. and Meharb, S.R. (2010):** The latent effect of certain Insecticides on pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella*, (Saund.). J. Adv. Agric. Res. (Fac. Ag. Saba Basha), 15(1): 57-75.
- Shekeban, M.M.K.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Abo El-Amayem, M. M.; Kassem, S. M. I.; Mancee, A. H. and El-Arami, S. A. (2009):** Monitoring Organophosphorous Resistance in pink bollworm Using the Attracticide Resistance Monitoring Technique. Resistant Pest Management Newsletter, 18(2): 31-36.
- Shekeban, M.M.K.; Al-Beltagy, A.M.; Abo El-Amayem, M. M.; Kassem, S. M. I.; Mancee, A.H. and El-Arami, S. A. (2009):** Monitoring organophosphorous resistance in pink bollworm using the attracticide resistance monitoring technique. Resistant Pest Management Newsletter, 18(2): 31-36.

- Shoeb, M.A.; Atalla, F.A. and Matar, A.M. (2007):** Pathogenicity of the entomopathogenic nematodes *Steinernema abbasi* and *Heterorhabditis bacteriophora* to certain economic insect pests. Egyptian J. of Biological Pest Control, 16 (2): 99-102.
- Somaa, H.M.; El-Keblawy, M.S. and El-Tahawe, H.S. (2018):** Role of the Parasitic Mite, *Pyemotes Tritici* (La Greze-Fossat and Montane) (Acari: Pyemotidae), and certain weather factors in the natural mortality percentage of diapause larvae of pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) in cotton bolls and infestation rate by Pbw in the next year. Annals of Agric. Sci., Moshtohor., 56(4): 1083-1090.
- Storey, G. (1914):** Notes on large-scale experiments against the pink bollworm in cotton seed. Agricultural Journal Egypt, 4:115-124.
- Storey, G. (1916):** The Simons hot air machine for the treatment of cotton seed against the pink bollworm. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin 11, Entomology Section.
- Storey, G. (1917):** Machines for the treatment of cotton seed against the Pink Bollworm. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service, Entomology Section Bulletin 14.
- Storey, G. (1921):** The present situation with regard to the control of the Pink Bollworm in Egypt. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin 16.
- Storey, G. (1923):** Recent work on the pink bollworm. Cairo Science Journal, 11(108):15-20.
- Swailm, S.M.; and Ismail, I.I. (1975):** Control effects of some new organic insecticides against the cotton bollworms *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 9:217-223.
- Taher, S.H. and Rashad, A.M. (1990):** Effect of photoperiod on different stages of the spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* Boisd. (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Annals of Agricultural Science (Cairo), 35:993-1000.
- Tawfik, M.F.S. and Awadallah, K.T. (1970):** The biology of *Pyemotes herfsi* Oudemans (Acarina: Pyemotidae) and its efficiency in the control of the resting larvae of the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders), in U.A.R. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 54:49-71.
- Tawfik, M.F.S. and El-Sherif, S.I. (1974):** The status of dead cotton bolls as a source for infestation on cotton plants with *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 58:191-196.
- Tawfik, M.F.S.; El-Husseini, M.M. and Awadallah, K.T. (1984):** Interactions between certain host larvae and the pyemoted ectoparasite, *Pyemotes tritici*. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 63:181-189.
- Templeton, J. (1925):** Ratoon cotton in Egypt. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Botany Section Bulletin 55.
- Templeton, J. (1928):** The perennial cultivation of cotton with special reference to the cultivation of ratoon in Egypt. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin 75.
- Templeton, J. (1932):** Watering and spacing experiments with Egyptian cotton. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin 112.
- Von Boguslawski, C. and Basedow, T. (2001):** Studies in cotton fields in Egypt on the effects of pheromone mating disruption on *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) (Lep.: Gelechiidae), on the occurrence of other arthropods, and on yields. Journal of Applied Entomology, 125:327-331.

One hundred ten years (1911 – 2021) of bollworms bibliography in Egypt

- Watson, W.M. and Guirguis, M.W. (1983):** Laboratory and field studies on the efficiency of granular insecticides against cotton pests. In 10th International Congress of Plant Protection, Proceedings of a Conference, Brighton, England, November 20–25, Plant Protection for Human Welfare, p. 944. Croydon, England: British Crop Protection Council.
- Watson, W.M.; Abbassy, M. and Zein, A.A. (1981):** Control effects of some new pyrethroids against the cotton bollworms *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund) and *Earias insulana* (Boisd) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Journal of Agricultural Research (Alexandria), 29:1511–1517.
- Watson, W.M.; Rashad, A.M. and Hussein, N.M. (1986):** Potencies of certain insecticides against the pink bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.), as influenced by chemical control programs in Egypt. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 15:79–86.
- Willcocks, F.C. (1916a):** The Insect and Related Pests of Egypt. Vol. 1. The Insect and Related Pests Injurious to the Cotton Plant. Part L. The Pink Bollworm. Cairo: Sultanic Agricultural Society.
- Willcocks, F.C. (1916b):** What effect has the flooding of a cotton field by infiltration from high Nile on the numbers of Pink Bollworm in that field. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 4:105–108.
- Willcocks, F.C. (1919c):** Experiment in Egypt on the survival of the Pink Bollworm in ripe damaged cotton bolls buried at different depths. In T.B. Fletcher, ed., Proceedings, 3rd Entomology Meetings, Pusa, pp. 532–547. Calcutta: Superintendent Government Printer.
- Willcocks, F.C. (1913):** An acarine parasite of the pink bollworm. Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, 2:68–72.
- Williams, C.B. (1926):** Seasonal variation in pink bollworm attack on cotton in Egypt in the years 1916–1924. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Technical Science Service Bulletin 67.
- Williams, C.B. (1922):** The pink bollworm in Egypt in 1922. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Cotton Research Board, Annual Report, 3(1):8.
- Williams, C.B. (1927):** Destruction du ver rose dans les graines de coton en Egypte. Bull. Union Agric. Egypt, 25:51–56.
- Williams, C.B. (1933):** Bollworms of cotton. Empire Cotton Growing Review, 10:273–281.
- Williams, C.B. (1934):** Field studies on the relation of insect pests to climatic conditions with special reference to cotton. In Report, 2nd Conference Cotton Growers Problems, pp. 111–125. London: Empire Cotton Growing Corp.
- Williams, C.B. and Bishara, I.E. (1925):** Survival of the pink bollworm larvae in buried seed during the winter in Egypt. Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt, Bulletin 58.
- Younis, A.M.; Soliman, M.A.; Khidr, A.A. and Gergis, M.F. (1988):** Prediction the time of different developmental stages of the spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) on the basis of heat unit accumulation. Minia J. Agric. Res. and Dec., 10(4): 1553- 1562.
- Zaki, A.A. and Hegab, M.E. (2013):** Evaluation of the effectiveness of some compounds on the pink and spiny bollworms in cotton fields. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 4(1): 83-89.
- Zaki, A.A.; Amer, A.E. and El-Sayed, A.A. (2017):** Effect of selected host plants on susceptibility of the American bollworm *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner) for some insecticides. J. Plant Prot. And Path., Mansoura Univ., 8(4):151-153.

Zeid, M.; Said, A.F.; Saad, A.K.; Madkour, A. and Soliman, S. (1972): Ground application of certain ULV concentrate with ultra-low-volume technique against the cotton leaf worm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) and

cotton bollworm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saund.) and *Earias insulana* Boisd. (Lepidoptera). Bulletin of the Entomological Society of Egypt, Economic Series, 6:187–194.

Instruction to authors

Original articles are full length papers describing original research. The paper should not exceed 15 pages of double-spaced typed text (including abstract, tables, figures and references). One double-spaced typed page contains approximately 300-350 words. Reviews are normally by invitation from the Editor-in-Chief. However, authors are encouraged to submit a tentative title and a table of contents of a proposed review for consideration. These reviews should not exceed 20 pages of double-spaced typed text (Including abstract, tables, figures and references). Scientific notes and short communications to the Editor usually on matters of general concern to plant protection, are welcome but should not exceed 4 typed pages. The decision to publish submitted scientific notes and short communications with the Editor-in-Chief.

Manuscripts should be written in clear, concise, and grammatically correct English. Submission of a manuscript implies: that the work described has not been published before; that it is not under consideration for publication anywhere else. Authors should submit their manuscripts online. To the Email: shaabanabdrabou59@yahoo.com

Manuscript preparation

Title: The title should reflect the most important aspects of the article, in a preferably concise form of not more than 150 characters and spaces. By-line The authors' names should be followed by affiliations and addresses.

Abstracts are required for all the manuscripts. They should be typed in one paragraph and limited to max.150- 200 words. The abstract should not contain any undefined abbreviations or unspecified references.

Keywords: Most important words of paper. Should be from 4 to 6 words.

Text: Main text should contain (1) an Introduction (2) a Material and Methods (3) a Results (4) a Discussion (5) a Conclusion (6) a References

Text formatting: Use a normal, plain font (e.g., 14 Point Times Roman) for text.

Abbreviations should be defined at first mention and used consistently thereafter. Authors should adhere to the rules governing scientific nomenclature to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. All biotica (crops, plants, insects, birds, mammals, etc.) should be identified by their scientific names including authors (and Order: Family) when the English term is first used in the main text, with the exception of common domestic plants and animals. Scientific names should be as follows: In the Title only give the Latin name but No authority or (Order: Family); in the Abstract all Latin names should be accompanied with the correct authority and with (Order: Family); in addition, at the first mention in the body of the text - and only then - these data should be given; authority, the order, family, should also go in the Key Words list.

Footnotes

Footnotes on the title page are not given reference symbols. Footnotes to the text are numbered consecutively; those to tables should be indicated by superscript lower-case letters (or asterisks for significance values and other statistical data).

References

The list of References should only include works that are cited in the text and that have been published or accepted for publication. Personal communications and unpublished works should only be mentioned in the text.

Cite references in the text by name and year in parentheses. Some examples:

- Negotiation research spans many disciplines (Abd-Rabou, 1996).
- This result was later contradicted (Simmons and Abd-Rabou, 2009).
- This effect has been widely studied (Abd-Rabou, 1998; Simmons *et al.*, 2002; Evans and Abd-Rabou, 2005 and Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2005).

List style

Reference list entries should be alphabetized by the last names of the first author of each work.

Journal article

Abd-Rabou, S. (1998): The efficacy of indigenous parasitoids in the biological control of *Siphoninus phillyreae* (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) on pomegranate in Egypt. Pan-Pacific Entomologists, 74 (3): 169-173.

Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005): Two new species and additional records of Egyptian Aphelinidae. Zootaxa, 833:1-7.

Simmons, A. and Abd-Rabou, S. (2006): Whitefly populations in vegetables crops with different fertilizers. 52nd Annual meeting of the South Carolina Entomological Society, Mc Cormick, Sc., October 19-20.

Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A. M. (2012): *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) whitefly as a pest in Egypt. Advances In Agricultural Research In Egypt, 10 (1): 1-82.

Figures Line-drawing should be clear and of high quality. Cite all figures in numerical order in the manuscript.

Tables The title should be self-explanatory and include enough information so that each table is intelligible without reference to the text or other tables. The title should summarize the information presented in the table without repeating the subheadings. Subheadings should be brief, nonstandard ones can be explained in footnotes. Cite tables in numerical order in the manuscript. Information presented in a table should agree with that in the text.